

Visualization Tool for Chemical Kinetic Pathways in Plasma-Assisted Combustion

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Science

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Abstract

Chemical kinetic mechanisms for combustion are represented by hundreds of reactions and tens of species. By introducing plasma discharges to combustion, the plasma chemistry can be exploited to enhance combustion regimes that are difficult to stabilize. In the context of plasma-assisted combustion, energetic electrons prompt electron impact reactions that provoke excitation in the mixture. By employing plasma-assistance, the combustion processes can be modified to achieve high-speed combustion as well as combustion with low emissions. Because computational simulations of these kinetic mechanisms have to account for the many reactions and species, the main numerical barrier lies in solving a stiff system of equations that includes the mass and energy conservation equations for all relevant species. In higher dimensional computational models, runtimes can take upwards of several hours even when the programs for these simulations are parallelized and run on supercomputer clusters. By understanding how each of the reaction pathways in the kinetic model influence the results of the simulation, an algorithm that determines the importance of each reaction can be developed. By generating an algorithm that can quantitatively assess the importance of the reaction to relevant values of the simulation such as ignition delay time (IDT), the overall kinetic model of plasma-assisted combustion and other plasma-based kinetic models can be interpreted in large parametric explorations and, subsequently, can be reduced. Ultimately, a reaction pathways analysis can be used as a kinetic model reduction tool for the simulated engineering design toolbox already present in the Aerospace Plasma Group at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Plasma-assisted Combustion Kinetics Overview

Plasma-assisted technologies are a field of study that involve the exploitation of plasma chemistry or dynamics to enhance the effective results of a kinetic process. In particular, plasma-assisted combustion is a technology that utilizes plasma chemistry to reduce emissions and enhance lean burn flame stability [1]. When a plasma discharge is used to facilitate the combustion of a gas, there are both non-thermal and thermal processes that instigate the combustion reaction or allow for flame stabilization. The non-thermal processes that occur are the transfer of momentum caused by the electrostatic forces from plasma, electron impact reactions that induce dissociation and ionization of the gas, and ion and electron drift. The thermal processes are separated into inhomogeneous and homogeneous heating of the gas provoked by vibrational and electron relaxation. The inhomogeneous heating creates perturbations in the gas which results in mixing and turbulent effects of the flow, whereas the homogeneous heating accelerates the chemical reaction effects [2].

Figure 1.1 depicts nanosecond repetitively pulsed plasma discharge (NRPD) introduced to an ammonia combustion process. It can be resolved that the NRPD effects cause the flame shape to appear stronger, stabilizing downstream even for lean mixtures such as in (e)

Figure 1.1: (a) Experimental setup schematic of nanosecond repetitively pulsed discharge (NRPD) plasma-assisted ammonia combustion, (b) no plasma, $\phi = 0.94$, (c) with plasma, $\phi = 0.94$, (d) no plasma, $\phi = 0.71$, (e) with plasma, $\phi = 0.71$ [3].

which possesses an equivalence ratio of $\phi = 0.71$ [3]. All NRPD systems utilize a reduced-electric field signal to excite and ionize relevant species, inciting the plasma chemistry for the particular kinetic mechanism. The reduced-electric field is a measure of the strength of the electric field E relative to the number density n . Reduced-electric field signals are typically decomposed into two timescales: pulse and interpulse. Pulse periods occur on the ns timescale, plasma chemistry occurs allowing for thermal and non-thermal plasma kinetic processes to occur. Pulse periods are characterized by an increase in the reduced-electric field either in the form of a Gaussian pulse as depicted in Figure 1.2 or a square-wave. In Figure 1.2, a Gaussian pulse signal is repeated during each pulse period with a maximum reduced-electric field of $\frac{E}{N_{max}} = 180 \text{ Td}^1$. Interpulse periods occur on the μs timescale, combustion chemistry occurs allowing for O radicals formed in pulse period to undergo combustion processes. Interpulse periods are characterized by no reduced-electric field such that $\frac{E}{N}(t) = 0 \text{ Td}$.

The effects of the plasma discharge on a combustion reaction can be quantified by the

¹The Townsend unit is a measure of the reduced-electric field and quantifies the rate of production of ions in a gas.

Figure 1.2: Graphical representation of the pulse and interpulse timescales of the reduced electric field of a nanosecond repetitively pulsed plasma discharge as a function of time.

ignition delay time (IDT), which is defined as the time necessary for a mixture of a fuel and an oxidizer to react and initiate the combustion reaction. In Figure 1.3, a combustion reaction using the GRI3.0 methane combustion mechanism is depicted. Running with an initial temperature of $T_0 = 1000$ K and a maximum simulation runtime of $t_{max} = 2$ s, it can be noted that the IDT occurs at the point where the rate of change of temperature is greatest, or when methane mole fraction has been completely consumed.

Ultimately, this insinuates that plasma-assistance yields the promise to enhance the ability to stabilize and manipulate lean and low temperature flames.

1.2 Problem Statement

The production and consumption of species, better known as the reaction pathways, in combustion kinetics is well-understood. With the complexity of coupled plasma-combustion kinetics, reaction pathways of excited, ionized, and ground-state species must be tracked to understand which plasma chemical reactions are most important in a coupled plasma-

Figure 1.3: Graphical representation of the zero-dimensional temperature profile for a stoichiometric methane combustion process using the GRI3.0 mechanism, an initial temperature of $T_0 = 1000$ K, and constant pressure.

combustion system. This project will build a numerical tool to quantify and visualize the reaction pathways in plasma-assisted combustion for two applications: interpretation of large parametric explorations of numerical experiments and reduction of chemical kinetic models for numerical efficiency.

1.3 Motivation

Experimental research of plasma-assisted combustion can help inform researchers of the effects of parametric modifications in the controls of the reaction. Although, if the parametric modification in equivalence ratio, plasma discharge signal, plasma chemistry, or any other relevant variable is novel, the effects on the combustion reaction may be difficult to predict. Therefore, simulations facilitate the design of experimental studies and real-world systems for plasma-assisted combustion. Because of the inherent complexity in the coupled transport processes and chemistry of the combustion reaction and the plasma chemistry, higher dimensional simulation models must resolve accurate time and spatial dependent values. In

Equation 1.1, the Boltzmann's equation is depicted.

$$\frac{\partial f_s}{\partial t} + \vec{w} \cdot \nabla f_s + \frac{\vec{F}_s}{m_s} \cdot \nabla_w f_s = \Sigma \int_{w_1} \int_{\Omega} (f'_s f'_{r1} - f_s f_{r1} g \sigma_{rs}) d\Omega d^3 w_1 \quad (1.1)$$

The Boltzmann equation must be solved for the electrons based on the input plasma chemistry and will ultimately produce a distribution function f_{e-} .

This distribution function is the probability of finding electrons with specific properties, such as position and velocity, at a particular point in $6D$ phase space. Additionally, the distribution function describes how electrons are distributed in this space. Furthermore, continuity equations such as species conservation and energy conservation equations must be solved for all species in the plasma and combustion kinetics. Because of the computational obstacles present in solving the Boltzmann equation and continuity equations, the trade-off for higher resolution is increased runtime and, thus, even programs parallelized for supercomputer clusters can take upwards of several hours. Because of the computational nature of the subsystem of the more extensive simulation engineering tool that this thesis aims to develop, the immediate effects of the resultant kinetic model reduction and reaction pathways analysis program poses a unique benefit to the greater extent of public health, safety, and welfare. By allowing researchers to better understand the effects of parametric changes on plasma-assisted combustion reactors, the future of chemically-powered aerospace could be altered altogether. The use of nanosecond repetitively pulsed plasma discharges could be used to allow for lean burn flame stability in aerospace vehicles. With enhanced lean burn stability, aerospace vehicles could use less fuel, which would decrease the toxic fuel emissions of large planes or jets. Therefore, environmentally, plasma-assisted combustion is poised to reduce the need to use potentially harmful chemical reactions that release emissions that damage the atmosphere. This extends to the ultimate effects on global, cultural, and social contexts because, this endeavor could bolster international and domestic means of transportation by allowing for cleaner air travel. It is important to note that the resultant effects of this endeavor could cause a greater upfront cost for aerospace vehicles that need to

supply plasma discharges to combustion chambers. This would include a nanosecond pulse generator that could provide a pulse repetition frequency (PRF) of approximately 100 kHz and a power supply. Although, because less fuel will be used over the course of the aerospace vehicle's lifetime, the total cost at the end of the aircraft's life will be lower than due to lower fuel purchases.

Because the intended stakeholders of this thesis are researchers in the field of aerospace plasma physics and engineering, this endeavor will serve as a modular engineering tool that extends existing plasma-assisted combustion simulation programs as a post-processing tool and will allow them to better grasp the effects of each reaction in the plasma chemistry pertaining to the specific simulation being run. This will allow for a detailed output that describes the most relevant reaction pathways that exist for a particular kinetic mechanism. This reaction pathways analysis could then be leveraged to parametrically and algorithmically reduce the input kinetic model. If the kinetic model is reduced and the results are preserved, the simulation will then inherently have a decreased computational runtime and therefore utilize less computational power. This will grant these researchers an ease in simulation analysis and thus analysis of plasma physics interactions with chemical kinetics.

1.4 Client and End User

The client for this project is the Aerospace Plasma Group at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology under the guidance of Professor Carmen Guerra-Garcia. However, the end user of this thesis could potentially be any plasma-assisted combustion or plasma physics researcher or system engineer. The overall problem faced by the end user regards the exhaustive and resource-intensive runtimes necessary to solve the many partial differential equations to collect the time and spatial dependent values of the plasma-assisted combustion interaction. This thesis would provide the end users with the capability to better understand the relevant reactions in the plasma-assisted combustion or plasma-coupled reaction simulation

and reduce the overall runtime by neglecting insignificant reactions.

Chapter 2

Numerical Modeling of 0D

Plasma-assisted Combustion Kinetic Pathways

2.1 Mathematical Model

All existing technology leverage a computation of element flux and, therefore, an in-house tool that uses a mathematical model to compute element flux can be created. Gao et al. [4] discusses a means to compute element flux between a species i and a species j as first designed by Revel et al. in 1994 [5]. In this study, the total element flux between species i and j for all reactions r can be computed as described in Equation 2.1

$$A_{i \rightarrow j} = \sum a_{r, i \rightarrow j} \quad (2.1)$$

The element flux for a specific reaction r can be solved via Equation 2.2

$$a_{r, i \rightarrow j} = \max(0, C_{r, i \rightarrow j} \dot{R}_r) \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.1: Reaction pathway diagram for an arbitrary kinetic mechanism that includes arbitrary species leveraged from the Gao et al. model [4].

In this equation, \dot{R}_r represents the instantaneous reaction rate for reaction r and $C_{r,i \rightarrow j}$ represents the number of atoms transferred between the i th and j th species for the r th reaction. $C_{r,i \rightarrow j}$ can be solved using Equation 2.3.

$$C_{r,i \rightarrow j} = \begin{cases} \frac{n_{r,i} n_{r,j}}{N_r}, v_{r,i} v_{r,j} < 0 \\ 0, \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (2.3)$$

In Equation 2.3, $n_{r,i}$ and $n_{r,j}$ represent the total number of atoms transferred between the i th and j th species in reaction r and N_r represents the total number of atoms transferred in the r th reaction. Furthermore, $v_{r,i}$ and $v_{r,j}$ represent the stoichiometric coefficients in the r th reaction where reactant coefficients are positive and product coefficients are negative. With this model, Gao et al. is able to determine which species are the most relevant as it pertains to element flux by producing a chart as depicted in Figure 2.1 [4].

2.2 Existing Technology

There exists numerous reaction pathway analysis tools and methodologies. In this section, the relevant open-source tools that leverage the previously discussed mathematical model for element flux to determine the significant reactions in a coupled combustion kinetic mechanism will be discussed.

2.2.1 Cantera

Cantera is an open-source tool that possesses built-in libraries to solve problems relevant to transport processes, chemical kinetics, and thermodynamics. Cantera's `ct.ReactionPathDiagram(gas, element)` function allows for a reaction path flow chart to be created. This chart exhibits a network of non-normalized element fluxes based on the net reaction rates for a species of interest at a specified input time. In Figure 2.2, a reaction pathway analysis that follow C for a combustion process using the GRI3.0 mechanism is generated from Cantera's built-in function.

It must be noted that this function cannot leverage the many reversible reactions that are present in combustion chemistry and cannot be easily coupled to plasma chemistry. Cantera uses an object-oriented methodology to handle the numerous input species and reactions inherent to the kinetic mechanism file, however, Cantera does not possess the ability to manage plasma species and plasma chemical reactions such as electron collision reactions. This is due to Cantera's inability to access cross-sectional data for excited states of relevant species and to solve for the electron distribution function necessary to describe rates for reactions that depend on electron temperature T_{e^-} .

2.2.2 CHEMKIN

CHEMKIN is a software package used for modeling and simulating complex chemical reaction mechanisms, particularly in the context of combustion and chemical kinetics. CHEMKIN

Figure 2.2: Reaction path diagram of reactions with an element of interest, C as produced by Cantera for the GRI3.0 combustion kinetic mechanism with an initial temperature $T_0 = 1000$ K until ignition occurs.

Figure 2.3: Reaction path diagram of reactions from CHEMKIN’s RPA tool [6].

is a subsidiary tool to ANSYS. Built into CHEMKIN is the Reaction Path Analyzer (RPA) visualization tool that visually displays the network of reactions that consume or produce species of interest. First, species of interest are selected to run sensitivity perturbation simulations on. Then, a plot representing the initial point in the premixed solution will be generated. The boldness of arrows represents the flux between species. Different times of interest can be selected via the Solution No. drop-down. Quantitative values for the production of a species of interest can be found in the lower left corner and normalized sensitivity values of a species of interest can be found in the lower middle as depicted in Figure 2.3.

Similar to Cantera, it must be noted that CHEMKIN cannot be easily coupled to plasma chemistry. Furthermore, CHEMKIN does not possess the ability to manage plasma species and plasma chemical reactions such as electron collision reactions. This is due to CHEMKIN’s inability to access cross-sectional data for excited states of relevant species and to solve for the electron distribution function necessary to describe rates for reactions that depend on electron temperature T_e . Additionally, CHEMKIN is not open-source and

requires integration with an off-the-shelf graphical user interface. This deters users from employing arbitrary chemical kinetics and disallows for adaptability in software.

2.2.3 PumpKin

PumpKin is an open-source software tool used to determine the most significant reaction pathways in chemical and plasma kinetic mechanisms. PumpKin leverages a computational algorithm for element flux to analyze the production and/or destruction rates of an input kinetic mechanism when a stoichiometric matrix, list of chemical reactions, list of stoichiometric coefficients, and the time evolved concentration and reaction rates are input [7]. Element flux is a measure of the production and consumption of atomic pathways in units of $\frac{mol}{cm^3s}$. PumpKin was built with ZDPlasKin users in mind, and thus uses QTPlasKin files as inputs. QTPlasKin is a post-processing tool, built to leverage the Fortran inherent to the Boltzmann Equation solver, ZDPlasKin. Data collected from the plasma chemistry can be utilized as input and can, ultimately, produce a detailed table of the most relevant reaction pathways. A species of interest *interest*, a start and end time range $[t_{init}, t_{end}]$, a maximum number of node branching points max_{bp} , a maximum lifetime for all species $\tau_{lifetime}$, a maximum number of pathways max_{path} , and a minimum element flux f_{min} are needed to produce the relevant fluxes for all production and destruction reactions present in the chemical mechanism of interest. It must be noted that PumpKin does not possess a built-in visualization tool and, instead, opts for relevant pathways and flux data to be printed to the terminal for the user to digest.

2.2.4 FluxViewer++

FluxViewer++ is a software tool used to visualize reaction pathways for combustion kinetics developed by the Laboratory of Molecular Structure and Dynamics and the Chemical Kinetics Laboratory of Eötvös Loránd University in Budapest, Hungary. By leveraging the element flux model described in Section 2.1, FluxViewer++ can read data files from Optima++,

Figure 2.4: Graphical user interface and sample reaction pathways diagram generated from FluxViewer++. The sample displays the major reaction pathways for a methane-air combustion process where the element tracked is C [8].

which is a separate software that carries out solutions for the continuity equations relevant to the combustion transport processes for a particular kinetic mechanism. Optima++ can generate element flux values for each reaction in a particular chemical mechanism which can be handed over to FluxViewer++ to visualize the inherent reaction pathways.

Figure 2.4 depicts the major reaction pathways in a methane-air combustion process such that the C -atom element fluxes are tracked. It can be seen that FluxViewer++ can visualize the reaction pathways as a function of time and can provide animations of the important pathways as the kinetic process occurs. However, FluxViewer++ lacks the capability to handle plasma chemistry such as electron collision reactions and does not possess the ability. Similar to Cantera and CHEMKIN, Optima++ cannot access cross-sectional data for excited states of plasma species and to solve for the electron distribution function necessary to describe rates for reactions that depend on electron temperature T_e .

Chapter 3

System Design

3.1 Technical Objectives

3.1.1 Design-Independent Technical Objectives

Table 3.1 defines the relevant design independent specifications for a robust reaction pathway analysis post-processing tool for plasma-assisted combustion. First, the tool developed in this thesis must be capable of identifying all of the reaction pathways for an input combustion mechanism and plasma mechanism. This insinuates that the tool must also be capable of tracking which species and reactions exist in the coupled plasma-combustion mechanism and, therefore, the tool must be capable of solving for these reaction pathways within a minimum boundary of typical kinetic input files. Thus, the tool must be capable of handling input files that record at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species. For the combustion mechanism GRI3.0, this chemical kinetic input lists 325 reactions and 53 species [9]. Next, the tool must be capable of visualizing the reaction pathways in such a way that minimizes edge-crossing and does not expend computational resources beyond what is expected of a singular numerical experiment. Typically, numerical experiments of plasma-assisted combustion possess a runtime of approximately 5 minutes; therefore, to minimize the computational resources spent for the post-processing visualization of the reaction pathways,

Requirement	Specification	Value
Identification of main reaction pathways	To interpret the results of large parametric sweeps by identifying the main reactions responsible for the enhancement.	Solve within the parameter space of at least 100 reactions and 50 species.
Post-processing visualization tool	To intuitively and efficiently plot the main reaction pathways.	Possess a runtime that is less than 10% of the simulation runtime: 30 seconds.
Reduced simulation runtime	To execute wide parametric sweeps, runtime of numerical experiments must be optimized.	At least 50% runtime reduction.
Sustained ignition delay time results of transport processes	By reducing the kinetics model, it is important to maintain the same level of model accuracy as the prior model developed by APG.	Within 250% of the original ignition delay time.

Table 3.1: Design-independent specifications for the reaction pathways analysis algorithm

the tool developed in this thesis must attribute a runtime of less than 10% of the the average numerical experiment runtime: 30 seconds or less. Furthermore, for chemical kinetic model reduction applications, the software must be capable of reducing simulation runtime by at least 50 %. This will allow for less computational resources to be expended and will allow for numerical experiments to be executed quicker. Lastly, for chemical kinetic model reductions, the results of transport processes must be retained within a reasonable range. For the purposes of this thesis, the transport process result of interest has been determined as the ignition delay time. The ignition delay time can help quantify the efficiency of the combustion process in 0D and, therefore, when the chemical kinetic model is reduced, the reduced kinetic mechanism must be sustain the ignition delay time within 250% of the original ignition delay time.

3.1.2 Design-Dependent Technical Objectives

Design dependent specifications depend particularly on the coupling between software used in the Aerospace Plasma Group and the software the thesis writer intends to use in this study. The design dependent specifications can be seen in Table 3.2. First, the software package developed in this thesis must be modular. This means that tool must be able to read any input file for both the chemical combustion kinetics and plasma discharge kinetics, regardless of the application. In the Aerospace Plasma Group, there are several research projects that exist, leveraging plasma and combustion kinetics; therefore, the tool must be able to read the already standardized files for chemical kinetics, `.yaml`, and for plasma kinetics, `.inp`. Similar to the first design-independent specification, this specification must also solve within the similar parameter space of common kinetic input files: at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species. Secondly, the visualization tool must leverage a mathematical model that can solve for element flux given a time-dependent data for each species number density and each reactions' reaction rate. This must also work with the common input files that possess at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species.

3.2 Final Design

3.2.1 Approach

A robust post-processing tool that outlines the significant reaction pathways by reading input reactions, species, and instantaneous reaction rates was developed. The intent is that an object-oriented Python software will be created to input arbitrary plasma kinetic mechanisms and combustion kinetic mechanisms. The object-oriented methodology will allow reactions and species to be easily related to reaction rates, reaction rate coefficients, reaction type, relevant reactant species, relevant product species, and other pertinent thermodynamic properties.

Requirement	Specification	Value
Model modularity	The tool must be able to analyze and reduce the kinetic model of a wide range of chemical and discharge chemistry combinations as APG is working on many different plasma modeling tools.	Solve within the parameter space of at least 100 reactions and 50 species.
Mathematical model	Build a mathematical model that has the modular ability to solve for element flux.	Must work for reverse and forward reactions and kinetic mechanisms that possess at least 100 reactions and 50 species.

Table 3.2: Design-dependent specifications for the reaction pathways analysis algorithm

Figure 3.1: Block diagram describing the interactions between programs for reaction pathway identification and visualization.

In Figure 3.1, it can be noted that chemical kinetic mechanism files serve as inputs in the form of `.yaml` files. These chemical kinetic mechanism files are read into memory using Cantera and object instances are created for each reaction under the `chemicalReaction` class. Similarly, plasma kinetic mechanism files also serve as inputs in the form of `.inp` files. These plasma kinetic mechanism files are also read into memory, but using a program developed in this thesis to relate plasma chemistry to the programming nomenclature used by Cantera. Object instances for each plasma chemical reaction are created under the `chemicalReaction` class. From each `chemicalReaction` object, species relevant to the reaction are read into memory as instances of the `chemicalSpecies` class. From each `chemicalReaction` object, `chemicalSpecies` objects can be compared on the reactants and products side of the reaction equation, for a given element of interest, to identify all relevant pathways. Using user-input plasma data, which includes the reaction rate coefficients and number densities of all plasma species as functions of time, and combustion data, which includes the temperature, time, reverse reaction rates, and mole fractions of all combustion species as a function of time, element flux is computed. By leveraging the Python library `NetworkX`, a pathways diagram is visualized and flux data is produced in the form of a `.csv`.

3.3 Models

3.3.1 0D Plasma-assisted Combustion Numerical Simulation

Modeling efforts of the effect of the plasma on flame in a combustion reaction is arduous due to the many reactions relevant to a specific chemical combustion mechanism and a plasma kinetic mechanism as well as the different time scales associated with the plasma discharge, chemical mechanism, and diffusive transport processes. Plasma-assisted combustion simulation models typically take two approaches: solve the time and spatial values relevant to the plasma discharge kinetics and the combustion mechanics separately or to develop a

sophisticated fully-coupled 0D model with simplified understandings of the experiment selected. Sharma et al. employs the first method by solving the partial differential equations relevant to the plasma and combustion chemistry in 2D, separately. The model then inputs the plasma discharge chemistry as initial conditions for the combustion chemistry [10]. Lefkowitz et al. employs the second method by developing a 0D fully-coupled modeling tool that can predict the behavior of a methane, oxygen, and helium mixture combustion reaction [11]. The Aerospace Plasma Group at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology has developed a 0D model of coupled plasma discharge kinetics and combustion kinetics as well as a 1D transient model to simulate the behavioral effects of the flame interacting with an NRP discharge [12]. The Aerospace Plasma Group’s engineering tool can be used to predict the behavioral effects of the plasma discharge on the flame. The plasma discharge kinetics are solved by making use of the open-source low-temperature plasma modeling tool, ZDPlasKin. ZDPlasKin was developed in Laboratoire des Plasmas et Conversion d’Energie (LAPLACE) and is used to solve the zero-dimensional plasma discharge chemistry regarding the conservation of species by utilizing an embedded Boltzmann equation solver, BOLSIG+. The program is natively written in Fortran, but APG has constructed a Julia wrapper for ease of computational manipulation. The combustion mechanics is solved using the open-source package Cantera which is natively written in C++. APG has also contributed a Julia wrapper for the combustion mechanics solver. In Figure 3.2, a schematic for APG’s coupled low-temperature plasma-chemical combustion kinetics modeling tool is shown.

For the purposes of this thesis, all operating conditions will exist within the zero-dimensional model. This implies that the gas mixtures relevant for this numerical modelling approach will be homogeneous and, therefore, there will be no spatial dependence for these simulated gaseous mixtures. Furthermore, for combustion kinetics, a constant pressure, fixed-mass reactor is utilized.

In Figure 3.3, a diagram for the numerical experimental setup of a constant pressure, fixed-mass reactor is described. In code, the Cantera reactor object `IdealGasReactor` is

Figure 3.2: The Aerospace Plasma Group’s coupled low-temperature plasma-chemical combustion kinetics modeling tool [12].

Figure 3.3: Constant pressure, fixed-mass reactor for homogeneous gas mixtures [13].

utilized and simulated to, first, solve for the mass conservation equation, Equation 3.1, to resolve a function for the mole fraction of each combustion species as a function of time.

$$\frac{d[X_i]}{dt} = \dot{\omega}_i - [X_i] \frac{1}{V} \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (3.1)$$

Next, the energy equation is solved, Equation 3.2, to resolve a function for the temperature as a function of time.

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{\left(\frac{\dot{Q}}{V}\right) - \sum_i \bar{h}_i \dot{\omega}_i}{\sum_i [X_i] \bar{c}_{p,i}} \quad (3.2)$$

For the plasma discharge kinetics, the 0D Plasma Reactor can collect the number densities for all excited, ionized, or other relevant species as well as the reaction rate coefficients as a function of time.

In Figure 3.4, it can be seen that experimental setups for NRPD include a combustion chamber and an electrode discharge source. This electrode discharge source is used to provoke the excitation and ionization of relevant species to a combustion process. In the 0D Plasma Reactor, this experimental setup is numerically simulated via the function `multipulse_solve()` and is used to solve the Boltzmann Equation which gathers the distribution function for electron. The electron distribution function can be used to solve for relevant instantaneous reaction rate coefficients.

In Figure 3.5, a numerical experiment with input conditions, $P_0 = 1$ atm, $PRF = 20$ kHz, $T_0 = 1000$ K, $\frac{E}{N_{max}} = 180$ Td, $N_{pulses} = 20$, $[X_{CH_4}]_0 = 0.09$, $[X_{N_2}]_0 = 0.72$, and $[X_{O_2}]_0 = 0.19$ is ran. It can be recognized that the number densities for all excited species are plotted as a function of time during the initial pulse period.

Figure 3.4: Nanosecond repetitively pulsed plasma discharge experimental setup [1].

Figure 3.5: Number densities for excited N species during the initial plasma discharge pulse.

3.4 Reaction Pathway Analysis Algorithm

3.4.1 Kinetic Mechanism Input File Reader

Because numerical experiments of plasma-assisted combustion must account for both the chemical reactions and the plasma chemical reactions between species relevant to a particular combustion process, input files that list the reactions, species, and thermodynamic properties for these reactions and species are utilized to streamline the numerical experimentation process. In the Aerospace Plasma Group, chemical kinetic mechanisms are stored in `.yaml` files and plasma kinetic mechanisms are stored in `.inp` files. Therefore, kinetic mechanism input file readers must be created for both kinds of kinetics.

Chemical Kinetic Mechanism Input File Reader

Because the 0D low-temperature plasma-chemical kinetic toolbox leverages Cantera to solve the continuity equations of mass conservation and energy conservation to resolve the time-dependent thermodynamic properties of the chemical combustion kinetics, a Python algorithm was developed that also uses Cantera to read the input `.yaml` files. Because of Cantera's object-oriented programming structure, the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` files can be directly read using Cantera's built-in functions. By wrapping these built-in Cantera functions into Python functions, the software developed in this thesis can retrieve a list of the species and reactions objects tracked in the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` files. For the purposes of the chemical kinetic mechanism input file reader developed as a part of this thesis software package, two functions were created: `get_species()` and `get_reactions()`.

`get_species()`

The `get_species()` function gathers all of the names species in the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` file and stores them as a list of strings. This function takes one parameter,

mechanism, which represents the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` file. From the `mechanism` parameter, the built-in Cantera function `ct.Species.list_from_file()` can be leveraged to create an array of Cantera species objects. The Cantera species objects possess attributes such as `composition`, which describes which element and how many atoms of the element compose each species, and `name`, which is a string describing the species. For the purposes of this wrapped function, each species name must be stored into the list. Therefore, the `get_species()` function iterates through the list of Cantera species objects to gather and append the name of each species into a secondary list. This list of species names is returned.

get_reactions()

The `get_reactions()` function collects all of the Cantera reaction objects in the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` file and stores them as a list of reaction objects. This function also takes one parameter, `mechanism`, which represents the input chemical kinetic mechanism `.yaml` file. From the `mechanism` parameter, the built-in Cantera functions `ct.Solution()`, which creates a gas object from the chemical kinetic mechanism, and `ct.Reaction.list_from_file()`, which creates a list of all of the Cantera reaction objects are utilized. The results of the latter Cantera function is returned. This list of Cantera reaction objects is used throughout the chemical combustion kinetics element flux and reaction pathways solver to better understand attributes of each reaction such as the reversibility, the reactants, the products, the reaction type, the reaction equation, and other key properties of each reaction.

Plasma Kinetic Mechanism Input File Reader

Because the 0D low-temperature plasma-chemical kinetic toolbox utilizes ZDPlasKin to solve the Boltzmann Equation for the distribution function of electrons and the continuity equations of mass conservation and energy conservation to resolve the time-dependent

thermodynamic properties of the plasma kinetics, a Python algorithm was developed that reads the input `.inp` files as text files to discern the species and reactions present in the input file. Because of Cantera's object-oriented programming structure, the input plasma kinetic mechanism `.inp` files was also stored into a species and reaction class developed in this thesis. For the purposes of the plasma kinetic mechanism input file reader developed as a part of this thesis software package, three functions and four classes were created: `read_inp()`, `find_species()`, `find_reactions()`, `reaction_objects()`, `class Reaction`, `class Equation`, `class Rate`, and `class Species`.

`read_inp()`

The `read_inp()` function reads and collects the text in the input plasma kinetic mechanism `.inp` file. By taking one parameter, `file_path`, which represents the file location to the `.inp` file, the input file can be read and returned as a string.

`find_species()`

The `find_species()` function isolates the data content representing the species tracked by ZDPlasKin in the input `.inp` file. This function takes one parameter, `inp_contents`, which represents the total text within the input `.inp` file in the form of a string. This function iterates through the string of `.inp` file content until the species identifier, "SPECIES", is discerned. Once the function reads "SPECIES", it identifies an initial line index where "SPECIES" is located and iterates until the species ending sequence is located, "END". The line index where "END" is located is collected and the species content within the `.inp` file is stored as a variable, `species_content`. The variable `species_content` is split into a string list of species, `species`, that are tracked by ZDPlasKin and returned by the function.

find_reactions()

The `find_reactions()` function locates the data content representative of the reactions tracked and utilized by ZDPlasKin in the input `.inp` file. This function takes one parameter, `inp_contents`, which represents the total text within the input `.inp` file in the form of a string. This function iterates through the string of `.inp` file content until the reactions identifier, "REACTIONS", is discerned. Once the function reads "REACTIONS", it identifies an initial line index where "REACTIONS" is located and iterates until the reactions ending sequence is located, "END". The resultant substring, `reactions_content`, is iterated through for each individual reaction and a subsequent dictionary is produced where the key is the parent reaction equation and the value is a list of length 2 representing the properties relevant to each equation. The first index in the value list is the reaction rate, followed by a dictionary of the variables within the `.inp` nomenclature. Variables in the input `.inp` files possess @ followed by a letter. Each variable in this dictionary is a key and the value is a list of all the possible values that can be filled by the variable. This allows the algorithm to associate coupled plasma reactions that form a singular reaction. This dictionary is returned as `reactions`.

class Reaction

`class Reaction` is an object class that allows the data within input `.inp` files to be associated in a streamlined manner. `class Reaction` allows reaction data to be associated with a particular reaction read from the previously discussed functions. `class Reaction` has three attributes: `equation`, `rate`, and `species`. These three attributes are also classes and describe the reaction equation, the reaction rate coefficient, and the species represented in the equation, respectively.

class Equation

`class Equation` is an object class that serves as an attribute for `class Reaction`. `class Equation` has two attributes: `template` and `reactions`. The attribute `template` is a string representing the reaction equation read directly from the `.inp` file. This string reaction equation can possess variables in the typical `.inp` format, starting with an `@`, but also can be a standard reaction equation. If the string reaction equation does not have variables the attribute `template` represents the overall reaction for that particular reaction. If the string reaction equation does have variables, the `template` is the reaction equation with variables within it. The second attribute is `reactions`, which is a string list of reactions with all corresponding variables replacing the placeholders within `template`. If `template` does not have variables, `reactions` will manifest as an empty list.

class Rate

`class Rate` is an object class that serves as an attribute for `class Reaction`. `class Rate` has two attributes: `template` and `rates`. Similar to `class Equation` the attribute `template` is a string representing the rate equation read directly from the `.inp` file. This string rate equation can possess variables in the typical `.inp` format, starting with an `@`, but also can be a standard rate equation. If the string reaction equation does not have variables the attribute `template` represents the overall rate for that particular reaction. If the string rate equation does have variables, the `template` is the rate equation with variables within it. The second attribute is `rates`, which is a string list of rate equations with all corresponding variables replacing the placeholders within `template`. If `template` does not have variables, `rates` will manifest as an empty list.

class Species

`class Species` is an object class that serves as an attribute for `class Reaction`. `class Species` has two attributes: `reactants` and `products`. The attribute `reactants`

represents a dictionary where the keys are reactant species in the particular reaction and the value is the number of the determined reactant species. Similarly, the attribute `products` represents a dictionary where the keys are product species in the particular reaction and the value is the number of the determined product species.

reaction_objects ()

The `reaction_objects ()` function leverages the collected species and reaction data from the input `.inp` file to create reaction objects using the classes discussed above. This function takes two parameters: `reactions`, representing the dictionary of reactions generated by `find_reactions ()`, and `species`, representing the string list of species tracked by ZDPlasKin generated by `find_species ()`. The parameter `reactions` is iterated through by accessing the list of keys within the dictionary. Each iteration a reaction object is generated and appended to a list, `reaction_objs`. This list of reaction objects is returned.

3.4.2 Pathway Identification Model

Because Cantera reaction objects have been seamlessly integrated with the object structure developed in this thesis for plasma chemistry, reaction pathway identification is the same process for reactions and species tracked solely by Cantera as well as for reactions and species tracked solely by ZDPlasKin. The function `pathway_identifier ()` has been developed as a means of determining whether a pathway has been discovered within a particular reaction. This function takes two parameters: `reaction`, representing the reaction object being searched for pathways, and `element_of_interest`, representing the string variable of the element that will be tracked for element flux. In Equation 3.3, a charge-exchange reaction between N_2^+ and O_2 to form N_2 and O_2^+ .

Equation 3.3 serves as an input into the function `pathway_identifier()` alongside an element to be tracked, `element_of_interest`. For the purposes of this example, N will be tracked. In the function, `pathway_identifier()`, the reaction object will be accessed to retrieve a dictionary of reactants and products. For this example, the reactants will be retrieved as: $\{N_2^+ : 1, O_2 : 1\}$. The products will be retrieved as $\{N_2 : 1, O_2^+ : 1\}$. The energy produced on the products side of the reaction equation is ignored. From there, the function will iterate through each reactant by accessing the list of keys in the reactants dictionary. For each reactant, each individual character in the reactant string is iterated through and checked if the character is a digit. If the character is not a digit, each product is iterated through by accessing the keys in the products dictionary. If the current reactant character is in the product, the current reactant and the current product are not the same species, and the element of interest is in both the reactant and the product, the pathway between the current reactant and product is generated and appended to a list, `pathways`. For the example described in Equation 3.3, it can be discerned that with an element of interest of N , the only pathway that will be generated is $N_2^+ \rightarrow N_2$. Thus, a list of length 1 will be generated containing the pathway $N_2^+ \rightarrow N_2$. This process can be done for all reactions in the coupled plasma-combustion kinetic mechanism via the function `collect_pathways()`. Similar to `pathway_identifier()`, takes two parameters: `reactions`, representing the list of reaction objects being searched for pathways, and `element_of_interest`, representing the string variable of the element that will be tracked for element flux. This function iterates through the list of reaction objects, leveraging the function `pathway_identifier()`, and outputs a dictionary of reaction pathways, `pathways`, where the key is the reaction object and the value is the list of pathways relevant to the particular reaction.

3.4.3 Reaction Rate Computation

Combustion Kinetic Mechanism Reaction Rate Computation

To solve for the reaction rate for each reaction within the combustion kinetic mechanism, a computational algorithm must be utilized. For the purposes of the software package developed in this thesis, it is assumed that all time-dependent reaction rate coefficients are defined by the Arrhenius equation. Equation 3.4 describes the Arrhenius equation such that A_i is the pre-exponential factor, E_{a_i} is the activation energy, and b_i is the temperature exponent for reaction i .

$$k_i(t) = A_i T_i(t)^{b_i} e^{-\frac{E_{a_i}}{RT_i(t)}} \quad (3.4)$$

In Cantera reaction objects, reaction rate coefficient properties are stored as attributes. Therefore, using a Python Cantera wrapper function was utilized to acquire A_i , E_{a_i} , and b_i . This function is defined as `get_rate_constants()` and takes one parameter: `reaction`, the reaction object for reaction i . Using this reaction rate coefficient property data, a second Python Cantera wrapper function, `Arrhenius()` can be created that leverages Equation 3.4. This function takes three parameters: `T`, the time-dependent gas temperature, `rate_constants`, the reaction rate coefficients gathered from `get_rate_constants()`, and `R`, the universal gas constant. Ultimately, the time-dependent reaction rate defined by Equation 3.4 is returned. Therefore, to solve for the time-dependent reaction rate for reaction i , Equation 3.4 must be leveraged.

$$q_i(t) = k_i(t) \prod_{w=1}^{N_r} \frac{y_w p_0}{N_A k_B T(t)} \quad (3.5)$$

Equation 3.5 describes the time-dependent reaction rate for reaction i such that the time-dependent reaction rate coefficient is defined by $k_i(t)$, Avogadro's number is defined by N_A , and the number densities for each reactants is converted from mass fraction to number density using the ideal gas law.

This process is wrapped in the function `solve_reaction_rate()` which takes eight parameters: `reverse_rate_coeff_data`, representing the reverse reaction rate data, `pathway`, representing the pathway in question, `rate_constants`, representing the reaction rate coefficient constants, `T`, representing the time-dependent gas temperature, `R`, representing the universal gas constant, `P0`, representing constant gas pressure, `chi_data`, representing the time-dependent mass fraction data for all species tracked by Cantera. First, the function parses through the reaction in order to determine if the pathway is from the standard reaction equation or the reversed equation. If the pathway is from the standard reaction equation, the function leverages Equation 3.3 to solve for the time-dependent reaction rate coefficient. If the pathway is from the reversed reaction equation, the function leverages data from `reverse_rate_coeff_data` for reaction i . From there, the time-dependent mass fractions for each reactant in reaction i are converted to time-dependent number densities using the ideal gas law and Equation 3.3 is solved for.

Plasma Kinetic Mechanism Reaction Rate Computation

In order to determine the reaction rate for each reaction within the plasma kinetic mechanism, a calculation that leverages the ZDPlasKin output time-dependent reaction rate coefficients for each reaction and the time-dependent number densities for species tracked by ZDPlasKin must be constructed. This computation is guided via Equation 3.6 for time-dependent plasma reaction rates.

$$q_i(t) = \frac{k_i(t)}{N_A} \prod_{w=1}^{N_r} n_w \quad (3.6)$$

In Equation 3.6, the output ZDPlasKin time-dependent reaction rate coefficient is defined by $k_i(t)$, Avogadro's number is defined by N_A , the product of all reactants' number densities is depicted from the remainder of the expression. The time-dependent reaction rate coefficient for each reaction within the plasma kinetic mechanism is different, but can be constant, a function of the electron temperature T_{e^-} , a function of the gas temperature

T_{gas} , or defined by the cross-sectional data for the relevant species. This culminates to the instantaneous reaction rate of $q_i(t)$, for reaction i . This process is wrapped in the function `solve_reaction_rate()` which takes three parameters: `rate_str`, representing the reaction rate string that defines the column in the input data, `reactants`, representing the list of strings that include all reactants, and `plasma_data`, representing the plasma data to be parsed for time-dependent reaction rates and number densities. For reaction i , $k_i(t)$ is accessed from the Pandas DataFrame `plasma_data` and each reactant string is iterated through to access the respective species' number density data. Using Equation 3.6, each relevant dataset is substituted into and computed numerically to provide a time-dependent array of reaction rate values for reaction i .

3.4.4 Element Flux Calculation

The element flux calculation takes inspiration from the mathematical model described by Gao et al. and is leveraged for combustion and plasma reactions [4]. First, a computation for the element flux for a reaction i is constructed as in Equation 3.7.

$$\dot{A}_{i,j \rightarrow k} = \text{mean}(q_i(t)) \frac{\nu_{A,j} \nu_{A,k}}{\nu_{A,i}} \quad (3.7)$$

In Equation 3.7, the element flux for a reaction i between a pathway j to k is computed. $\nu_{A,j}$ and $\nu_{A,k}$ represent the total number of an input element of interest A (N , O , C , or H) in reactant node j and product node k , respectively. Whereas, $\nu_{A,i}$ represents the total number of the element of interest A in reaction i . Lastly, $q_i(t)$ represents the time-dependent reaction rate for reaction i as described above. The process to acquire the element flux multipliers, $\nu_{A,j}$, $\nu_{A,k}$, and $\nu_{A,i}$ are wrapped in the function `atom_transfer_multiplier()`. This function takes three parameters: `element`, representing the element A to track, `reaction`, representing the reaction object for reaction i , and `pathway`, the relevant pathway between reactant node j and product node k . First, the function accesses the reaction dictionary

in order to determine the total number of reactant node j species that exist in reaction i . Then, the function iterates through the string of characters for reactant node j in order to determine the multiplier of element A in reactant node j . The product of these two values is defined as $\nu_{A,j}$. Next, the function repeats this process for the product node k in order to solve for $\nu_{A,k}$. Lastly, the function iterates through both the reactants and products, independently. In each individual looping process, the reactants' and products' string of characters are iterated through to count the total number of element of interest A that exist in the total reaction i . This value is returned as $\nu_{A,i}$. Equation 3.7 is then utilized for each reaction relevant to the pathway between reactant node j to product node k and summed over all reactions of length N_r . The mean value within this time space is taken as the relevant element flux for this pathway as described in Equation 3.8.

$$\bar{A}_{i,j \rightarrow k} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} A_{i,j \rightarrow k} \quad (3.8)$$

3.4.5 Reaction Pathways Visualization

To visualize the element flux provided by the equations and software package described in prior sections, the Python library NetworkX is utilized. The approach taken in this thesis is to visualize the reaction pathways through a force-directed graph. Force-directed graphing techniques position nodes in two-dimensions to minimize edge crossing by simultaneously minimizing a global energy function. The global energy function is acquired by assuming that each node behaves like a spring and possesses attractive forces to node that share an edge using Hooke's law, whereas nodes that do not share an edge possess repulsive forces similar to electrically charged particles using Coulomb's law as seen in Figure 3.6.

NetworkX can provide a force-directed graphing algorithm via the Kamada and Kawai method. NetworkX provides this functionality through the function `neato` allowing this thesis to generate force-directed reaction pathway diagrams. NetworkX was wrapped in the Python function `network_plotter()`, which takes one parameter: `flux_dict`, repre-

Figure 3.6: Force-directed graph visualization assuming attractive and repulsive forces guide the global energy function of nodes [14].

senting the element flux dictionary where the key is the pathway in question and the value is the element flux in units of $\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$ for the pathway between reactant node j and product node k .

Chapter 4

Design Validation

Validation studies have been executed on both the combustion and plasma pathway analysis tools built in this thesis. These studies were decoupled to assess the operational capabilities of identifying species in plasma and combustion chemistry models.

4.0.1 Well-Stirred Reactor

For the purposes of this design validation, a well-stirred reactor was selected to isolate combustion chemistry processes. Well-stirred reactors are defined as isothermal, isobaric, isochoric, and homogeneous environments that eliminate the spatial distribution of species encountered in flames.

As depicted in Figure 4.1, well-stirred reactors are defined by Equation 4.1:

$$\frac{\partial m_{i,cv}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}^m V + m_{i,in} \dot{m} - m_{i,out} \dot{m} \quad (4.1)$$

It can be recognized that well-stirred reactors possess both a control volume and a control surface that takes a constant mass flow rate, an initial mass fraction for each species, and an initial enthalpy for each species in and the same mass flow rate, a final mass fraction for each species, and a final enthalpy for each species out after reaching the residence times τ . It can also be recognized that the temperature T , pressure P , and volume V do not evolve

Figure 4.1: Schematic of a well-stirred reactor [13].

with time. In order to acquire data for a simulation tool was developed in Python to acquire the thermodynamic and transport properties as they evolve in time for the high temperature case. This simulation tool leverages the Cantera library.

In Figure 4.2, it can be discerned that first, a combustion kinetic mechanism takes each species within the gas mixture and collects them into individual mixture tanks. These mixture tanks are then injected into the well-stirred reactor via a mass flow controller. The

Figure 4.2: Schematic of the Cantera representation of a well-stirred reactor [15].

purpose of the mass flow controller is used to ensure a constant mass flow of each species into the well-stirred reactor. Between $t = 0$ s and a residence time of t_{res} , the mass fraction is gathered. On the outlet of the well-stirred reactor, the pressure is kept constant via a pressure valve. Ultimately, the gas mixture is collected in a capture tank reservoir.

4.0.2 High Temperature Combustion Validation

In order to assess the capability of the combustion pathways analysis three key factors must be validated and analyzed: pathway identification, reaction rate computation, and important reaction pathway identification. For the purposes of this validation study, a low-temperature experimental pathway diagram was selected from An Introduction to Combustion: Concepts and Applications by Stephen Turns [13].

As seen in Figure 4.3, a high-temperature methane combustion reaction pathway diagram has been created from experimental data. The numerical experiment was ran in a well-stirred reactor at 2200 K, a stoichiometric nitrogen-air mixture, a pressure of 1 atm, and with a residence time of 0.1 s. This high temperature case was studied individually and similar data was collected in order to mirror the behaviors denoted in these figures. High temperature methane combustion was simulated using an ancestral GRI3.0 mechanism, GRI2.11 [13].

Using the previously discussed methodologies to compute the reaction rates were taken and particular reactions were selected to compare to as detailed in Figure 4.5.

As we can see from both the high-temperature validation study, the tool developed in this thesis is capable of calculating the reaction rate at the end of residence time t_{res} within approximately the same order of magnitude as detailed by the technical specifications. Furthermore, it should be noted that outliers in the computational comparison of reaction rate exist for reactions 53, 58, 61, and 146. This is most likely due to differences in the experimental setup from Turns [13] and the Cantera setup described in Figure 4.2. In the Turns data, there is no distinguishing value for inlet concentration of fuel, oxidizer, or dilution. Thus, the numerical representation of the well-stirred reactor setup assumes inlet

Figure 4.3: High temperature reaction pathway diagram for the combustion of methane [13].

Figure 4.4: Time-dependent mass fractions for all species tracked that are tracked by GRI2.11.

Figure 4.5: Comparison between experimental reaction rate data and algorithmically simulated reaction rate data.

Figure 4.6: Reaction pathways diagram for the high temperature combustion mechanism.

concentrations of $CH_4 = 9\%$, $O_2 = 19\%$, and $N_2 = 72\%$. Because of these potential errors, it is plausible to assume the reaction rates computed for reactions 53, 58, 61, and 146 are outliers. It is also salient to note that the code developed for this validation study can both take in arbitrary inputs and run with a maximum computational time of approximately 10 seconds. Pathway identification was validated by generating a network diagram and comparing to Figure 4.3.

In Figure 4.6, an element of interest of C is selected, and it can be recognized that pathways between CO_2 and CO , $CH_2(S)$ and CO_2 , as well as CO_2 and CH_2 are most relevant. Similar to Figure 4.3, the pathways with a reaction rate greater than $10^{-7} \frac{mol}{cm^3s}$ are verified in the program developed in this thesis. Furthermore, the element flux is upheld such that the most relevant pathways in Figure 4.3 are similarly depicted in Figure 4.6.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

The software package developed in this thesis is evaluated through two user-cases: visualization of numerical experiments and kinetic model reduction.

5.1 Visualization of Numerical Experiments

Numerical experiments of plasma-assisted combustion systems can take a number of unique parametric inputs. Plots can be created for both the chemical kinetic mechanism of choice *GRI3.0*, which contains 53 species and 325 reactions, and the plasma kinetic mechanism of choice, `kinet_CH4_PAC_V5_nrg.inp`, which contains 27 species and 51 reactions. This allows us to verify the design-independent technical objective of identification of main reaction pathways within a parameter space of at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species. Furthermore, because the model can take any arbitrary `.yaml` file as input for a chemical kinetic mechanism and any arbitrary `.inp` file as input for a plasma kinetic mechanism and identify all reaction pathways within a parameter space of at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species, the design-dependent technical objective of model modularity is also verified. A parameter of interest for better understanding how plasma kinetics can improve ignition is inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute mole fractions. In Figure 5.1, a large parameter sweep of CH_4 , O_2 , and N_2 inlet mole fractions has been executed. In order to understand which plasma

Figure 5.1: Gradient plot of ignition delay time over a large parameter space of inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute mole fractions.

kinetic pathways are playing roles in ignition enhancement, the software packaged developed in this thesis can be leveraged.

In Figure 5.1, a particular case was selected; stoichiometric methane combustion, with inlet concentrations of fuel, oxidizer, and dilution of $CH_4 = 9\%$, $O_2 = 19\%$, and $N_2 = 72\%$. From the plasma data and a selected element of interest of O , a pulse and interpulse network diagram can be constructed at the 15th pulse and interpulse period in Figure 5.2.

It should be noted that the most relevant pathways in the pulse period are those that incite the ionization of ground-state species, such as O_2 to O_2^+ and in the interpulse period are those that invoke dissociative quenching such as O_2^+ to O . In Figure 5.2, it can be discerned that, during the pulse period, the most important pathway exists between O_2 to O_2^+ with an element flux greater than $10^2 \frac{mol}{cm^3s}$. This pathway is followed directly by the pathway between H_2O^+ to H_2O , interactions between O_2 to H_2O , H_2O^+ to H_2O , and H_2O^+ to O_2^+ , the pathway between O_2^+ to O , the pathway between O_2 to O , and interactions between

Figure 5.2: Reaction pathways diagram for the 15th pulse and interpulse period with an element of interest of O .

O_2 to CO_2 , CO_2^+ to CO_2 , and CO_2^+ to O_2^+ . It can be noted that the lowest element flux tracked during the 15th pulse period is on the order of magnitude of $10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. During the interpulse period, the most important pathway exists between O_2^+ and O_2 with an element flux greater than $10^{-4} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. The importance of this pathway is followed by the pathway between O_2^+ to O_2 and O_2 to O ; where the lowest element flux tracked is on the order of magnitude of $10^{-23} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Therefore, it can be stated that more O_2^+ molecules are being created during the pulse period than quenched during the interpulse period.

Similarly, from the plasma data and a selected element of interest of N , a pulse and interpulse network diagram can be constructed at the 15th pulse and interpulse period in Figure 5.3.

It should be noted that the most relevant pathways in the pulse period are those that involve ionized N_2 and higher-order excited states of N_2 . These pathways are N_2^+ to N_2 , N_2 to N_2^+ , N_2 to $N_2(a)$, $N_2(B)$, $N_2(C)$, or $N_2(A)$ and the reverse pathways of these pathways. These pathways possess element fluxes as high as $10^1 \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$ and as low as $10^{-5} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. The next most important reaction pathways are those that involve ladder-down operations between excited N_2 species. These pathways possess element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-9} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Lastly, interactions between higher-order excited states of N_2 possess the least

Figure 5.3: Reaction pathways diagram for the 15th pulse and interpulse period with an element of interest of N .

important element flux reaction pathways as low as $10^{-18} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. During the interpulse period, it can be seen that the de-excitation pathway between $N_2(v_1)$ to N_2 is most relevant. This is because $N_2(v_1)$ is the lowest order excited state tracked in this plasma chemistry model, meaning that quenching effects that produce N_2 are most prevalent in the interpulse period with an element flux as high as $10^{-18} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Next, are de-excitation pathways between higher order excited states of N_2 and ground-state N_2 . This can be depicted through the pathways, $N_2(a)$ to N_2 and $N_2(A)$ to N_2 , with element flux values on the order of magnitude of $10^{-23} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Next, are de-excitation interactions between higher-order excited states of N_2 . These pathways are $N_2(a)$ to $N_2(B)$ and $N_2(B)$ to N_2 with element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-28} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. These pathways are followed by additional de-excitation pathways between higher-order excited states of N_2 . These pathways are $N_2(A)$ to $N_2(B)$ and $N_2(A)$ to $N_2(C)$ with element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-42} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Subsequently, the least important reaction pathways in the interpulse period exist in the de-excitation and anomalous excitation pathways between lower order excited states of N_2 with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-46} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}}$. Therefore, it can be stated that more excited states of N_2 molecules and ionized molecules of N_2 are being created during the pulse period than quenched during the interpulse period.

Furthermore, from the plasma data and a selected element of interest of H , a pulse and

Figure 5.4: Reaction pathways diagram for the 15th pulse and interpulse period with an element of interest of H .

interpulse network diagram can be constructed at the 15th pulse and interpulse period in Figure 5.4.

During the pulse period, it can be distinguished that the most relevant reaction pathway is the ionization pathway from H_2O to H_2O^+ with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^2 \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. This pathway is followed in importance by the reaction pathway that involves the de-ionization of H_2O from H_2O^+ to H_2O with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{0.5} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. Next, the pathway that involves H dissociation from an ionized state of CH_4 is noted from CH_4^+ to CH_3 with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-0.5} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. This pathway is followed by a similar H dissociation pathway from CH_4^+ to H with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-1.5} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. Next, is the pathway involving H dissociation from ground-state CH_4 with pathways CH_4 to CH_3 and CH_4 to H with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-2} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. The least important reaction pathway during the pulse period is distinguished as the ionization pathway from ground-state CH_4 to CH_4^+ with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. During the interpulse period, it can be discerned that the most relevant pathways are those that involve the dissociative quenching of CH_4^+ . These pathways are CH_4^+ to CH_3 and CH_4^+ to H with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. Subsequently, these pathways are followed in importance by pathways involving the dissociation of CH_4 in pathways of CH_4 to CH_3 and

Figure 5.5: Reaction pathways diagram for the 15th pulse and interpulse period with an element of interest of C .

CH_4 to H with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-20} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. Therefore, it can be stated that more ionized H -bearing molecules are being created during the pulse period than quenched during the interpulse period.

Lastly, from the plasma data and a selected element of interest of C , a pulse and interpulse network diagram can be constructed at the 15th pulse and interpulse period in Figure 5.5.

During the pulse period, it can be determined that the most relevant reaction pathways are those that involve ionized species. These pathways are CO_2 to CO_2^+ and CH_4^+ to CH_3 with element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-1} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. These pathways are followed in importance by subsequent de-ionization and ionization pathways of relevant species. These pathways are CO_2^+ to CO_2 , CH_4 to CH_4^+ , and CH_4 to CH_3 with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. Ultimately, the least important reaction pathway during the pulse period involves the dissociation of ionized CO_2 , a pathway of CO_2^+ to CO with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-5} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. During the interpulse period, it can be distinguished that the most important pathway is the quenching of CH_4^+ to CH_3 with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. This reaction pathway is followed in importance by dissociative quenching processes of CH_4 to CH_3 with an element flux on the order of magnitude of $10^{-21} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{s}}$. In Figure 5.6, it can be seen for the eight reaction pathway diagrams created that track elements O , N , H , and C all possess runtime less than 30 s; with

Figure 5.6: Runtime comparison of all reaction pathways diagrams tracking elements O , N , H , and C for both pulse and interpulse periods.

a maximum runtime for N being approximately 18 s. These visualization are made using datasets that contain time-dependent values for all reaction rate coefficients and number densities and are approximately 2 GB in size. Therefore, the design-independent technical objective to generate a post-processing visualization tool with an average runtime less than 30 s is verified such that the average runtime in this case study is 10.76 s. Furthermore, because a mathematical model was capable of describing the element flux within a parameter space of at least 100 reactions and at least 50 species such that each reaction pathway was provided a time-dependent function for element flux, the final design-dependent technical objective of developing a mathematical model for element flux is verified. Ultimately, from this case study of visualizing numerical experiments relating to plasma-assisted combustion, it can discern that reaction pathways can help researchers better understand which reaction pathways are activated when a plasma discharge is exposed to a gaseous combustion process.

Figure 5.7: Programming diagram representing the gradient-ascent optimization algorithm developed to maximize the reaction rate cutoff.

5.2 Kinetic Model Reduction

Kinetic model reduction for chemical combustion mechanisms is primarily used as a means to strip the chemical model of unnecessary transport processes and to isolate the important reactions. For the purposes of this thesis, a gradient-ascent-based optimization technique was leveraged to procedurally approximate the maximum reaction rate cutoff necessary to provide a chemical kinetic mechanism with an ignition delay time within 250% of the original ignition delay time.

In Figure 5.7, it can be seen that the gradient-ascent algorithm takes in an initial chemical kinetic mechanism and an initial target ignition delay time as input. These values are then substituted into a 0D combustion reactor via the Cantera object `IdealGasReactor()` with an initial temperature T_0 , a simulation duration t_{max} , and an inlet concentration of the fuel (CH_4), oxidizer (O_2), and dilute (N_2). This simulation is executed and mass fractions as a function of time and gas temperature as a function of time are retrieved. The ignition

Figure 5.8: Comparison between 0D temperature profile ignition delay time location and 0D rate of change of temperature ignition delay time location.

delay time is computed and checked against 250% of the target ignition delay time.

In Figure 5.8, it can be seen that an in-house ignition delay time algorithm was constructed to find the time where the rate of change of temperature is greatest. This time is returned as the ignition delay time. If the computed ignition delay time is greater than 250% of the target ignition delay time, the final reduced chemical kinetic mechanism is returned. If the computed ignition delay time is less than 250% of the target ignition delay time, a finite difference gradient ascent on the reaction rate cutoff is executed guided by Equation 5.1.

$$\zeta = \frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon} [|(IDT_C + \epsilon) - IDT_T| - |(IDT_C - \epsilon) - IDT_T|] \quad (5.1)$$

Using Equation 5.1, the reaction rate is increased by $\zeta * L.R.$, such that L.R. represents a parameter input for the learning rate. The learning rate allows the optimization algorithm to understand how quickly it should increase the reaction rate cutoff each iteration. From the increased reaction rate cutoff, the input chemical kinetic mechanism is reduced by finding the percent contribution of element flux of all reactions in the chem-

Gas Mixture	X_{N_2}	X_{O_2}	X_{CH_4}	Reactions Removed
1	0.8	0.11	0.09	34
2	0.84	0.12	0.04	13
3	0.72	0.19	0.09	45
4	0.6	0.22	0.18	57
5	0.67	0.25	0.08	11

Table 5.1: Gradient-ascent optimization on chemical kinetic mechanisms depicting the number of reactions removed for varying inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute concentrations.

ical kinetic mechanism. Any reaction with an element flux less than $100 * \min(\bar{A}_{i,j \rightarrow k})$ are removed via the in-house algorithm `process_yaml_file()`, which takes three input parameters: `input_file_path`, representing the file path of the initial chemical kinetic mechanism, `reactions_to_remove`, representing the list of reactions to remove, and `output_file_path`, representing the file path that the updated `.yaml` file should be written to. This function reads the `.yaml` file as a `.txt` file for each reaction in `reactions_to_remove`, procedurally removing each reaction. Subsequently, the updated `.yaml` file is the `.yaml` file excluding all reactions in `reactions_to_remove`. This process was done for the input chemical kinetic mechanism used in validation GRI2.11 with parameteric constraints of $P_0 = 1$ atm, $T_0 = 1100$ K, $t_{max} = 1$ s. The results for this study are described in Table 5.1.

In Figure 5.9, it can be discerned that for each of the five gas mixtures studied, there was a relatively large reduction in runtime. On the left y -axis, the runtime in s is denoted and on the right y -axis, the runtime percent reduction is described. For all five gas mixtures, there is at least a 50% runtime reduction. Therefore, the design-independent technical objective to reduce simulation runtime with at least a 50% runtime reduction is verified. The concept of runtime reduction can be further described by visualizing the reaction pathways that are distinguished for the original chemical kinetic model and the reduced chemical kinetic

Figure 5.9: Comparison of original runtime of GRI2.11 mechanism and reduced GRI2.11 mechanism for varying inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute concentrations.

Figure 5.10: Comparison of original reaction pathways of GRI2.11 mechanism and the reduced reaction pathways of GRI2.11 mechanism for gas mixture 4.

model. For the purposes of this analysis, it is sufficient to look at the case that reduced the input chemical kinetic mechanism by the most reactions, gas mixture 4 in Table 5.1.

In Figure 5.10, it can be discerned that many reaction pathways from the original chemical kinetic mechanism have been eliminated via the 57 reactions removed when the element C is tracked. This leaves the reduced chemical kinetic mechanism with only interactions between HCO and CO_2 , HCO and CO , CO_2 and CO , as well as CO_2 and NCO to occur. This manifests as a shift in the ignition delay time for the original chemical kinetic mechanism and the reduced chemical kinetic mechanism as depicted in Figure 5.11.

Figure 5.11: Comparison of the ignition delay time using the original GRI2.11 mechanism and the ignition delay time using the reduced GRI2.11 mechanism for gas mixture 4.

Ultimately, the difference between the ignition delay time using the original GRI2.11 mechanism and the ignition delay time using the reduced GRI2.11 mechanism for gas mixture 4 is within 106%. This upholds the design-independent technical objective to sustain ignition delay time results of transport processes within 250% of the original ignition delay time.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

This thesis has described the design and implementation of a visualization tool for chemical kinetic pathways in plasma-assisted combustion numerical experiments. First, a literature view was performed to better understand the reaction pathway tools that exist and the potential improvements that could be made to an automated visualization tool for chemical kinetic pathways in plasma-assisted combustion numerical experiments. Therefore, four design-independent technical objectives were defined: capability to identify main reaction pathways within a parameter space of at least 100 reactions and 50 species, the creation of a post-processing visualization tool that attributes a runtime of less than 30 seconds, the ability to reduce simulation runtime for chemical kinetic mechanisms of at least 50% runtime reduction, and the capability to sustain ignition delay time results of transport processes for reduced chemical kinetic mechanisms within 250% of the original ignition delay time. Similarly, two design-dependent technical objectives were created: model modularity such that the automated program can access any arbitrary input chemical kinetic mechanism and plasma kinetic mechanism and a robust mathematical model. Through validation and user case evaluation, each of the four design-independent specifications were verified such that plots can be created for any arbitrary input chemical kinetic `.yaml` mechanism and input plasma kinetic `.inp` mechanism. Namely, both the chemical kinetic mechanism of choice

GRI3.0, which contains 53 species and 325 reactions, and the plasma kinetic mechanism of choice, `kinet_CH4_PAC_V5_nrg.inp`, which contains 27 species and 51 reactions, visualization of reaction pathways attributes a runtime of approximately 10.76 s, and chemical kinetic model reduction produces a runtime reduction of at least 50% with an error of approximately 106% of the initial ignition delay time. Through the computational lens that this engineering tool has developed, by allowing researchers to better understand the effects of parametric changes on numerical experiments of plasma-assisted combustion, design of chemically powered aerospace vehicles could be changed. The further application of plasma-assisted combustion in commercial aerospace vehicles could allow these vehicles to use less fuel and burn with the same efficiency as typical fuel consumption rates. With enhanced lean burn stability, this would decrease the toxic fuel emissions of large planes or jets. Therefore, from an environmental lens, plasma-assisted combustion could reduce the need to use potentially harmful fuels that release emissions that damage the atmosphere and, instead, use fuels that pose a much lesser threat such as ammonia. Therefore, global, cultural, and social contexts are effected such that international and domestic means of transportation could reduce total emissions, making travel much more accessible. Ultimately, the engineering tool and software package developed in this thesis is capable of visualizing reaction pathways in complex plasma-combustion kinetic mechanisms that better allow researchers to understand the effects of parametric changes in numerical experiments.

6.1 Future Work

In the future, more detailed parametric studies could be executed for a greater range of inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute concentrations. This would allow researchers to better grasp which reaction pathways are activated more effectively and for which inlet fuel, oxidizer, and dilute concentrations. Furthermore, the gradient-ascent optimization algorithm developed for kinetic model reduction can be extended to numerical plasma reactor setups such as the

0D low-temperature plasma-modeling toolbox developed by APG. This would be done by converting the Python optimization to be compatible with the 0D low-temperature plasma-modeling toolbox developed by APG, which involves the conversion from Python to Julia.

Appendix A

Combustion Reaction Pathways

Algorithm

Because this thesis involves entirely numerical software development, the costs relevant to this development are nothing.

Item	Cost
Plasma-assisted combustion 0D simulation toolbox	Provided by APG
TOTAL	0.00

Table A.1: Cost Breakdown

Appendix B

Combustion Reaction Pathways

Algorithm

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import networkx as nx
import cantera as ct
from scipy.constants import Avogadro
import matplotlib.colors as mcolors
from networkx.drawing.nx_agraph import graphviz_layout
from netgraph import Graph
from fuzzywuzzy import fuzz
import re

def get_species(mechanism):
    S = ct.Species.list_from_file(mechanism, section='species')
    species = []
    for i in S:
```

```

        temp_s = i.name
        species.append(temp_s)
    return species

def get_reactions(mechanism):
    gas = ct.Solution(mechanism)
    rxns = ct.Reaction.list_from_file(mechanism, gas)
    return rxns

def get_reaction_strings(mechanism):
    gas = ct.Solution(mechanism)
    rxns = ct.Reaction.list_from_file(mechanism, gas)
    reactions = []
    for j in rxns:
        temp_r = j.equation
        reactions.append(temp_r)
    return reactions

def pathways_identifier(reaction, reactants, products, element_of_interest):
    pathways = []
    temp_pathway = []
    for reactant in reactants:
        for char in reactant:
            if char.isdigit() == False:
                for product in products:
                    if char in product:
                        if reactant != product
                        and element_of_interest in reactant
                        and element_of_interest in product:

```

```

        temp_pathway = f"{reactant}->{product}"
    if temp_pathway not in pathways
    and temp_pathway == f"{reactant}->{product}":
        pathways.append(temp_pathway)
        if reaction.reversible == True:
            temp_pathway = f"{product}->{reactant}"
        if temp_pathway not in pathways:
            pathways.append(temp_pathway)

    return pathways

def find_pathways(reaction, element_of_interest):
    rxn_type = reaction.reaction_type
    rxn_eq = reaction.equation
    rate_constants = get_rate_constants(reaction)

    if rxn_type == "Arrhenius":
        reactants = list(reaction.reactants.keys())
        products = list(reaction.products.keys())
        temp_pathways = pathways_identifier(reaction, reactants,
        products, element_of_interest)
        pathways = {}
        if rxn_eq not in pathways:
            pathways[rxn_eq] = [reaction, temp_pathways]
        return pathways

    elif rxn_type == "three-body-Arrhenius":
        third_body = reaction.third_body efficienc
        reactants = list(reaction.reactants.keys())
        products = list(reaction.products.keys())
        pathways = {}

```

```

for species in list(third_body.keys()):
    rxn_name = rxn_eq.replace("M", species)
    temp_reactants = reactants.copy()
    temp_products = products.copy()
    temp_reactants.append(species)
    temp_products.append(species)
    temp_pathways = pathways_identifier(reaction, temp_reactants,
    temp_products, element_of_interest)
    if rxn_name not in pathways and temp_pathways != []:
        pathways[rxn_name] = [reaction, temp_pathways, species,
        float(third_body[species])]
    return pathways

def get_rate_constants(reaction):
    rxn_type = reaction.reaction_type
    if rxn_type == "Arrhenius":
        A = float(reaction.rate.input_data["rate-constant"]["A"])
        b = float(reaction.rate.input_data["rate-constant"]["b"])
        Ea = float(reaction.rate.input_data["rate-constant"]["Ea"])
        rate_constants = [A, b, Ea]
    else:
        rate_constants = [0, 0, 0]
    return rate_constants

def reverse_rate(data, reaction_eqn):
    return data[reaction_eqn]

def solve_reaction_rate(reverse_rate_coeff_data, pathway, reaction_obj,
rate_constants, T, R, P0, chi_data, efficiency=1):

```

```

reaction_type = reaction_obj.reaction_type
pathways = pathway.split("→")
j = pathways[0]
k = pathways[1]
reactants = []
for keyr in list(reaction_obj.reactants.keys()):
    for i in range(int(reaction_obj.reactants[keyr])):
        reactants.append(keyr)
products = []
for keyp in list(reaction_obj.products.keys()):
    for w in range(int(reaction_obj.products[keyp])):
        products.append(keyp)
k_t = 0
if j in reactants
and k in products
and reaction_type == "Arrhenius":
    k_t += Arrhenius(T[-1], rate_constants, R)

elif j in products
and k in reactants
and reaction_obj.equation in reverse_rate_coeff_data.columns
and reaction_type == "Arrhenius":
    k_t = reverse_rate(reverse_rate_coeff_data,
        reaction_obj.equation).to_numpy()[-1]
    reactants = []
    for keyr in list(reaction_obj.products.keys()):
        for i in range(int(reaction_obj.products[keyr])):
            reactants.append(keyr)
    products = []

```

```

    for keyp in list(reaction_obj.reactants.keys()):
        for j in range(int(reaction_obj.reactants[keyp])):
            products.append(keyp)

q_t = 1
for reactant in reactants:
    temp_mole_frac_str = "Y_" + reactant
    temp_instantaneous_mole_frac = chi_data[temp_mole_frac_str].to_numpy()
    temp_instantaneous_mole_frac = np.nan_to_num(
        temp_instantaneous_mole_frac,
        nan=0, posinf=0, neginf=0)
    q_t *= y2n(T, P0, temp_instantaneous_mole_frac)
if reaction_type == "three-body-Arrhenius" and k_t > 0:
    q_t *= (efficiency*1e6*k_t)
elif reaction_type == "Arrhenius" and k_t > 0:
    q_t *= (1e3*k_t)
return q_t[-1]

```

```

def atom_transfer_multiplier(element, reaction, pathway, third_body=None):
    vAj = 0
    vAk = 0
    vAi = 0
    j, k = pathway.split("<math>-></math>")
    reactants = reaction.reactants
    products = reaction.products
    if reaction.reaction_type == "three-body-Arrhenius":
        reactants[third_body] = 1.0
        products[third_body] = 1.0
    if j in reactants and k in products:
        vAj += float(reactants[j])

```

```

    vAk += float(products[k])
elif k in reactants and j in products:
    vAj += float(reactants[k])
    vAk += float(products[j])
filtered_reactant_keys = [key for key in reactants.keys() if key is not None]
for reactant in filtered_reactant_keys:
    if element in reactant:
        for idx in range(len(reactant)):
            char = reactant[idx]
            if char == element and idx + 1 < len(reactant):
                next_char = reactant[idx+1]
                if next_char.isdigit():
                    vAi += float(next_char)*float(reactants[reactant])
            else:
                vAi += 1.0*float(reactants[reactant])
            elif char == element and idx + 1 == len(reactant):
                vAi += 1.0*float(reactants[reactant])
filtered_product_keys = [key for key in products.keys() if key is not None]
for product in filtered_product_keys:
    if element in product:
        for idx in range(len(product)):
            char = product[idx]
            if char == element and idx + 1 < len(product):
                next_char = product[idx+1]
                if next_char.isdigit():
                    vAi += float(next_char)*float(products[product])
            else:
                vAi += 1.0*float(products[product])
            elif char == element and idx + 1 == len(product):

```

```

        vAi += 1.0*float(products[product])
    return [vAj, vAk, vAi]

def compute_pathway_flux(multiplier_constants, q_t):
    vAj, vAk, vAi = multiplier_constants
    multiplier = (vAj*vAk)/vAi
    Adot = q_t*multiplier
    return Adot

def Arrhenius(T, rate_constants, R):
    A, b, E = rate_constants
    k = A*T**b*np.exp(-E/(R*T))
    return k

def y2n(T, P0, y):
    n = (y*P0/(1.38e-23*T))/1e6
    n = n*(1/Avogadro)
    return n

def find_connecting_nodes(element_flux, central_node):
    pathways = list(element_flux.keys())
    connecting_nodes = []
    for pathway in pathways:
        j, k = pathway.split("<math>\leftrightarrow</math>")
        if j == central_node:
            connecting_nodes.append(k)
        elif k == central_node:
            connecting_nodes.append(j)
    return list(set(connecting_nodes))

```

```

def find_connecting_edges(element_flux):
    pathways = list(element_flux.keys())
    connecting_edges = []
    for pathway in pathways:
        j, k = pathway.split("↔")
        connecting_edges.append([j,k])
    return connecting_edges

def get_flux_dict(reactions, element_of_interest, reverse_rate_coeffs, T, R,
P0, chi, cutoff):
    pathways = {}
    for rxn in reactions:
        temp_pathway = find_pathways(rxn, element_of_interest)
        if temp_pathway is not None:
            pathways.update(temp_pathway)
        else:
            pass
    flux_dict = {}
    flux_contribution_dict = {}
    for rxn_str in list(pathways.keys()):
        rxn = pathways[rxn_str][0]
        temp_pathways = pathways[rxn_str][1]
        for path in temp_pathways:
            rate_constants = get_rate_constants(rxn)
            q_t = solve_reaction_rate(reverse_rate_coeffs, path, rxn,
rate_constants, T, R, P0, chi, efficiency=1)
            multiplier_constants = atom_transfer_multiplier(element_of_interest,
rxn, path)

```

```

flux = compute_pathway_flux(multiplier_constants, q_t)
if q_t > cutoff:
    if path not in flux_dict:
        flux_dict[path] = flux
    else:
        flux_dict[path] = flux_dict[path] + flux
if q_t > cutoff:
    if path not in flux_contribution_dict:
        flux_contribution_dict[path] = [{rxn_str: flux}]
    else:
        flux_contribution_dict[path].append({rxn_str: flux})
return [flux_dict, flux_contribution_dict]

```

```

def network_plotter(flux_dict):
    paths = list(flux_dict.keys())
    intensity = []
    for path in paths:
        temp_flux = flux_dict[path]
        intensity.append(temp_flux)
    intensity = np.array(intensity)
    plt.figure(figsize=(7.5,5))
    G = nx.MultiDiGraph()
    for i, pathway in enumerate(paths):
        source, target = pathway.split('→')
        G.add_edge(source, target, intensity=intensity[i])
    pos = nx.drawing.nx_pydot.graphviz_layout(G, prog='neato')
    nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos, node_color='white', node_size=100)
    cmap = plt.cm.turbo
    min_intensity = np.min(intensity)

```

```

max_intensity = np.max(intensity)
norm = mcolors.LogNorm(vmin=min_intensity, vmax=max_intensity)
for u, v, d in G.edges(data=True):
    edge_intensity = d['intensity']
    edge_color = cmap(norm(edge_intensity))
    nx.draw_networkx_edges(G, pos, edgelist=[(u, v)], arrowsize=12,
        edge_color=edge_color, connectionstyle="arc3,rad=0.125")
labels = {node: latexify(node) for node in G.nodes()}
nx.draw_networkx_labels(G, pos, labels=labels, font_color='black', font_size=8)
sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=mcolors.LogNorm(vmin=min_intensity,
vmax=max_intensity))
sm.set_array([])
cbar = plt.colorbar(sm, shrink=0.75)
cbar.set_label(r'Element-Flux- $(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3\text{-s}})$ ', labelpad=15)
plt.axis('off')
plt.show()

```

```

def latexify(str):
    latex = r"$" + re.sub(r'(\d)', r'_\1', str) + "$"
    return latex

def find_percent_flux(flux_dict, flux_contribution_dict):
    total_flux = 0
    for path in list(flux_dict.keys()):
        temp_flux = flux_dict[path]
        total_flux += temp_flux
    rxn_flux_percent = {}
    for pathway in list(flux_contribution_dict.keys()):
        for i in range(len(flux_contribution_dict[pathway])):

```

```

    for rxn in flux_contribution_dict[pathway][i]:
        temp_flux_percent = (flux_contribution_dict[pathway][i][rxn]
                             /total_flux)*100
        if rxn not in rxn_flux_percent:
            rxn_flux_percent[rxn] = temp_flux_percent
        else:
            rxn_flux_percent[rxn] = rxn_flux_percent[rxn]
            + temp_flux_percent

flux_arr = []
for rxn in list(rxn_flux_percent.keys()):
    temp_flux = rxn_flux_percent[rxn]
    flux_arr.append(temp_flux)
flux_arr = np.array(flux_arr)
min_flux = np.min(flux_arr)*10
if min_flux > 1:
    min_flux = 1
return [total_flux , rxn_flux_percent , min_flux]

def read_yaml(file_path):
    with open(file_path , 'r') as file:
        yaml_contents = file.read()
    return yaml_contents

def find_lower_priority_rxns(rxn_flux_percent , percent_cutoff):
    reactions_to_remove = []
    for rxn in list(rxn_flux_percent.keys()):
        temp_flux_percent = rxn_flux_percent[rxn]
        if temp_flux_percent < percent_cutoff:
            reactions_to_remove.append(rxn)

```

```

return reactions_to_remove

def find_three_body_rxn_strs(reactions):
    rxn_strings = []
    for reaction in reactions:
        if reaction.reaction_type == "three-body-Arrhenius":
            rxn_strings.append(reaction.equation)
    return rxn_strings

def replace_m(equation1, equation2):
    replacement_bool = False
    reactants1, products1 = equation1.split("<=>")
    reactants2, products2 = equation2.split("<=>")
    last_plus_index1 = reactants1.rfind("+")
    last_plus_index2 = reactants2.rfind("+")
    part1 = reactants2[last_plus_index2 + 2:]
    part2 = reactants1[last_plus_index1 + 2:]
    equation1_replaced = equation1.replace("M", part1)
    equation2_replaced = equation2.replace("M", part2)
    if equation1_replaced == equation2_replaced:
        replacement_bool = True
    return replacement_bool

def edit_reactions_to_remove(reactions_to_remove, three_body_rxns):
    filtered_reactions_to_remove = []
    count = 0
    temp_str = 0
    for rxn in reactions_to_remove:
        for three_body_rxn in three_body_rxns:

```

```

        if replace_m(rxn, three_body_rxn):
            count = 1
            temp_str = three_body_rxn
            break
    if count == 1:
        filtered_reactions_to_remove.append(temp_str)
    elif count == 0:
        filtered_reactions_to_remove.append(rxn)
    count = 0
return list(set(filtered_reactions_to_remove))

def isolate_reaction_string(line):
    match = re.search(r'equation:\s*(.*?)\s*#', line)
    if match:
        return match.group(1)
    return None

def parse_reaction(reaction_string):
    reactants, products = reaction_string.split("<=>")
    reactant_components = reactants.split("-+-")
    product_components = products.split("-+-")
    return set(reactant_components), set(product_components)

def contains_reaction(line, reaction):
    yaml_reaction_str = isolate_reaction_string(line)
    yaml_reactants, yaml_products = parse_reaction(yaml_reaction_str)
    temp_reactants, temp_products = parse_reaction(reaction)
    return temp_reactants == yaml_reactants and temp_products == yaml_products

```

```

def process_yaml_file(input_file_path, reactions_to_remove, output_file_path):
    with open(input_file_path, 'r') as input_file:
        lines = input_file.readlines()
        output_lines = []
        remove_reaction_block = False
        for line in lines:
            if remove_reaction_block:
                if "#-Reaction" in line:
                    remove_reaction_block = False
                    output_lines.append(line)
            else:
                if any(line.startswith('-equation:') and contains_reaction(line,
                    remove_reaction_block = True
                else:
                    output_lines.append(line)
        with open(output_file_path, 'w') as output_file:
            output_file.writelines(output_lines)

    return output_file_path

```

Appendix C

Plasma Reaction Pathways Algorithm

```
from plasma_chemistry import *
import numpy as np
from scipy.constants import Avogadro
from fuzzywuzzy import process
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import networkx as nx
import matplotlib.colors as mcolors
import re

def read_inp(file_path):
    with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
        inp_contents = file.read()
    return inp_contents

def find_species(inp_contents):
    lines_inp = inp_contents.splitlines()
    start = 0
    end = 0
```

```

for i in range(len(lines_inp)):
    temp_line = lines_inp[i]
    if "SPECIES" in temp_line:
        start = i
        counter = start
        while "END" not in lines_inp[counter]:
            counter += 1
        end = counter
    species_content = lines_inp[start+1:end]
    filtered_species_content = [element for element in species_content
    if "#" not in element and element != '']
    species = []
    for element in filtered_species_content:
        if '-' in element:
            species.extend(element.split())
        else:
            species.append(element)
    if "E" in species:
        index_electron = species.index("E")
        species[index_electron] = "e"
    return species

```

```

def find_reactions(inp_contents):
    lines_inp = inp_contents.splitlines()
    start = 0
    end = 0
    for i in range(len(lines_inp)):
        temp_line = lines_inp[i]
        if "REACTIONS" in temp_line:

```

```

start = i
counter = start
while "END" not in lines_inp[counter]:
    counter += 1
end = counter

reactions_content = lines_inp[start+1:end]
filtered_reactions_content = [element for element in reactions_content
if "=>" in element or "@" in element]
start = 0
end = 0
reactions = {}
for j in range(len(filtered_reactions_content)):
    temp_element = filtered_reactions_content[j]
    if "!" in temp_element:
        split_reaction_str = temp_element.split('!')
        first_str = split_reaction_str[0].strip()
        second_str = split_reaction_str[1].strip()
        start = j
        counter = start + 1
        while counter < len(filtered_reactions_content) and
("!" not in filtered_reactions_content[counter]
or "@" not in filtered_reactions_content[counter]):
            if "END" in filtered_reactions_content[counter]:
                break
            counter += 1
        end = counter
        data = [second_str]
        temp_data = {}
        for k in range(start+1,end):

```

```

temp_data_str = filtered_reactions_content[k].strip()
if "@" in temp_data_str:
    temp_key = temp_data_str[temp_data_str.index("@")+1]
    + temp_data_str[temp_data_str.index("@")+1]
    split_str_data = temp_data_str.split('=')
    split_str_specific = split_str_data[1].split()
    if temp_key not in temp_data:
        temp_data[temp_key] = split_str_specific
data.append(temp_data)
reactions[first_str] = data
return reactions

def reformat_rxns(rxn_eqn, data):
    additional_species = data[1]
    rate_constant = data[0]
    signifiers = list(additional_species.keys())
    modified_rxns = []
    modified_rate_constant = []
    for signifier in signifiers:
        if signifier in rxn_eqn:
            for species in additional_species[signifier]:
                temp_modified_rxn_eqn = rxn_eqn.replace(signifier, species)
                modified_rxns.append(temp_modified_rxn_eqn)
        if signifier in rate_constant:
            for species in additional_species[signifier]:
                temp_modified_rate = rate_constant.replace(signifier, species)
                modified_rate_constant.append(temp_modified_rate)
    rxns = {}
    for i in range(len(modified_rxns)):

```

```

temp_rxn = modified_rxns[i]
temp_rate = modified_rate_constant[i]
rxns[temp_rxn] = temp_rate
return rxns

```

```

def reaction_objects(reactions, species):
    reaction_objs = []
    for key in list(reactions.keys()):
        eqn = key
        val = reactions[key]
        rate = val[0]
        conditions = val[1]
        eqns = []
        rates = []
        if conditions:
            conditions_keys = list(conditions.keys())
            for key in conditions_keys:
                if key in eqn:
                    if len(eqns) == 0:
                        eqns = [eqn.replace(key, value)]
                        for value in conditions[key]
                    else:
                        for idx, rxn in enumerate(eqns):
                            temp_eqn = rxn.replace(key, conditions[key][idx])
                            eqns[idx] = temp_eqn
                elif key in rate:
                    if len(rates) == 0:
                        rates = [rate.replace(key, value)]
                        for value in conditions[key]

```

```

        else:
            for idx, rate in enumerate(rates):
                temp_rate = rate.replace(key, conditions[key][idx])
                rates[idx] = temp_rate
            reactant_data, product_data = format_species(eqns, species)
    else:
        conditions = None
        eqns = None
        rates = None
        reactant_data, product_data = format_species([eqn], species)
    temp_eqn_obj = Equation(eqn, eqns)
    temp_rate_obj = Rate(rate, rates)
    temp_species_obj = Species(reactant_data, product_data)
    temp_reaction_obj = Reaction(temp_eqn_obj,
    temp_rate_obj, temp_species_obj)
    reaction_objs.append(temp_reaction_obj)
return reaction_objs

```

```

def format_species(rxns, species):
    reactant_data = []
    product_data = []
    for rxn in rxns:
        temp_reactant = {}
        temp_product = {}
        for s in species:
            if s in rxn:
                components = rxn.split()
                index = components.index('=>')
                reactant_count = sum(1 for component in components[:index]

```

```

if component.strip() == s)
product_count = sum(1 for component in components[index+1:])
if component.strip() == s)
if reactant_count != 0:
    temp_reactant[s] = reactant_count
if product_count != 0:
    temp_product[s] = product_count
reactant_data.append(temp_reactant)
product_data.append(temp_product)
return [reactant_data, product_data]

```

```

def pathways_identifer(reaction, element_of_interest):
    pathways = {}
    temp_pathway = 0
    reactants = reaction.species.reactants
    products = reaction.species.products
    reactions = reaction.equation.reactions
    if reactions != None:
        for idx in range(len(reactions)):
            for reactant in list(reactants[idx].keys()):
                for char in reactant:
                    if char.isdigit() == False:
                        for product in list(products[idx].keys()):
                            if char in product:
                                index_char_reactant = reactant.index(char)
                                index_char_product = product.index(char)
                                if reactant != product
                                and element_of_interest in reactant
                                and element_of_interest in product

```

```

and reactant[index_char_reactant-1] != "("
and product[index_char_product-1] != ":
    temp_pathway = f"{reactant}->{product}"
if reactions[idx] not in pathways
and temp_pathway ==
f"{reactant}->{product}":
    pathways[reactions[idx]] =
[[temp_pathway, reactants[idx],
products[idx]]]
elif reactions[idx] in pathways
and temp_pathway == f"{reactant}->{product}"
and [temp_pathway, reactants[idx],
products[idx]] not in pathways[reactions[idx]]
    pathways[reactions[idx]].extend([[
temp_pathway, reactants[idx],
products[idx]])]
elif reactions == None:
    eqn = reaction.equation.template
for reactant in list(reactants[0].keys()):
    for char in reactant:
        if char.isdigit() == False:
            for product in list(products[0].keys()):
                if char in product:
                    index_char_reactant = reactant.index(char)
                    index_char_product = product.index(char)
                    if reactant != product
                    and element_of_interest in reactant
                    and element_of_interest in product
                    and reactant[index_char_reactant-1] != "("

```

```

and product[index_char_product-1] != "(":
    temp_pathway = f"{reactant}->{product}"
if eqn not in pathways
and temp_pathway == f"{reactant}->{product}":
    pathways[eqn] = [[temp_pathway, reactants[0],
                      products[0]]]
elif eqn in pathways
and temp_pathway == f"{reactant}->{product}":
and [temp_pathway, reactants[0],
      products[0]] not in pathways[eqn]:
    pathways[eqn].extend([[temp_pathway,
                           reactants[0], products[0]]])

return pathways

def collect_pathways(reactions, element_of_interest):
    pathways = {}
    for rxn in reactions:
        if "ANY_NEUTRAL" in rxn.equation.template:
            pass
        else:
            temp_pathways = pathways_identifier(rxn, element_of_interest)
            pathways.update(temp_pathways)

    return pathways

def solve_reaction_rate(rate_str, reactants, plasma_data):
    closest_match, similarity_score = process.extractOne(rate_str,
        plasma_data.columns.tolist())
    time = plasma_data["PDtt"].to_numpy()
    time_ct = plasma_data["PDtt_ct"].to_numpy()

```

```

[tt_pulse_bounds, tt_interpulse_bounds] = find_pulse_interpulse(15,
20e3, time)
tstart, tend = find_time_idx(tt_pulse_bounds, time)
rate_coeff_data = plasma_data[closest_match].to_numpy()[tstart:tend]
rate_coeff_data[np.isnan(rate_coeff_data)] = 0
k_t = rate_coeff_data
q_t = 1
for r in reactants:
    closest_match_reactant, similarity_score_reactant = process.extractOne(
    "n_" + r, plasma_data.columns.tolist())
    temp_n_data = plasma_data[closest_match_reactant].to_numpy()[tstart:tend]
    temp_n_data[np.isnan(temp_n_data)] = 0
    temp_n = temp_n_data
    q_t *= temp_n
q_t = (k_t*q_t)/Avogadro
q_t_f = np.mean(q_t)
return q_t_f

def atom_transfer_multiplier(reactants, products, element, pathway):
    vAj = 0
    vAk = 0
    vAi = 0
    j, k = pathway.split("<math>-></math>")
    if j in reactants and k in products:
        reactant_multiplier = 1
        product_multiplier = 1
        for char_r_idx in range(len(j)):
            char_r = j[char_r_idx]
            if char_r.isdigit() and j[char_r_idx-1] == element:

```

```

        reactant_multiplier = float(char_r)
    for char_p_idx in range(len(k)):
        char_p = k[char_p_idx]
        if char_p.isdigit() and k[char_p_idx-1] == element:
            product_multiplier = float(char_p)
    vAj += float(reactants[j])*reactant_multiplier
    vAk += float(products[k])*product_multiplier
elif k in reactants and j in products:
    reactant_multiplier = 1
    product_multiplier = 1
    for char_p_idx in range(len(k)):
        char_p = k[char_p_idx]
        if char_p.isdigit() and k[char_p_idx-1] == element:
            reactant_multiplier = float(char_p)
    for char_r_idx in range(len(j)):
        char_r = j[char_r_idx]
        if char_r.isdigit() and j[char_r_idx-1] == element:
            product_multiplier = float(char_r)
    vAj += float(reactants[k])*reactant_multiplier
    vAk += float(products[j])*product_multiplier
filtered_reactant_keys = [key for key in reactants.keys() if key is not None]
for reactant in filtered_reactant_keys:
    if element in reactant:
        for idx in range(len(reactant)):
            char = reactant[idx]
            if char == element and idx + 1 < len(reactant):
                next_char = reactant[idx+1]
                if next_char.isdigit():
                    vAi += float(next_char)*float(reactants[reactant])

```

```

        else:
            vAi += 1.0*float(reactants[reactant])
        elif char == element and idx + 1 == len(reactant):
            vAi += 1.0*float(reactants[reactant])
    filtered_product_keys = [key for key in products.keys() if key is not None]
    for product in filtered_product_keys:
        if element in product:
            for idx in range(len(product)):
                char = product[idx]
                if char == element and idx + 1 < len(product):
                    next_char = product[idx+1]
                    if next_char.isdigit():
                        vAi += float(next_char)*float(products[product])
                else:
                    vAi += 1.0*float(products[product])
            elif char == element and idx + 1 == len(product):
                vAi += 1.0*float(products[product])
    return [vAj, vAk, vAi]

```

```

def compute_pathway_flux(multiplier_constants, q_t):
    vAj, vAk, vAi = multiplier_constants
    multiplier = (vAj*vAk)/vAi
    Adot = q_t*multiplier
    return Adot

```

```

def find_rate_str(reaction_objs, reaction):
    rate_str = 0
    for reaction_obj in reaction_objs:
        temp_rxn_template = reaction_obj.equation.template

```

```

if reaction == temp_rxn_template and "@" not in temp_rxn_template:
    rate_str = reaction_obj.rate.template
    if "BOLSIG" not in rate_str:
        rate_str = reaction
    return rate_str
elif reaction_obj.equation.reactions != None:
    temp_rxn_strs = reaction_obj.equation.reactions
    temp_rate_strs = reaction_obj.rate.rates
    if len(temp_rate_strs) == 0:
        rate_str = reaction_obj.rate.template
        if "BOLSIG" not in rate_str:
            rate_str = reaction
        return rate_str
    else:
        for i in range(len(temp_rxn_strs)):
            temp_rxn = temp_rxn_strs[i]
            if temp_rxn == reaction:
                rate_str = temp_rate_strs[i]
                if "BOLSIG" not in rate_str:
                    rate_str = reaction
            return rate_str

def get_flux_dict(pathways_dict, reaction_objs, element_of_interest, plasma_data,
flux_dict = {}
reactions = list(pathways_dict.keys())
for rxn in reactions:
    temp_rate_str = find_rate_str(reaction_objs, rxn)
    for pathway_arr in pathways_dict[rxn]:
        pathway = pathway_arr[0]

```

```

    reactants = pathway_arr[1]
    products = pathway_arr[2]
    q_t = solve_reaction_rate(temp_rate_str, reactants, plasma_data)
    multiplier_constants = atom_transfer_multiplier(reactants, products, e
    flux = compute_pathway_flux(multiplier_constants, q_t)
    if q_t > cutoff:
        if pathway not in flux_dict:
            flux_dict[pathway] = flux
        else:
            flux_dict[pathway] = flux_dict[pathway] + flux
    return flux_dict

def latexify(str):
    latex = r"$" + re.sub(r'(\d)', r'_\1', str) + "$"
    return latex

def network_plotter(flux_dict, file_name, lower_bound, upper_bound):
    paths = list(flux_dict.keys())
    intensity = []
    for path in paths:
        temp_flux = flux_dict[path]
        intensity.append(temp_flux)
    intensity = np.array(intensity)
    G = nx.MultiDiGraph()
    for i, pathway in enumerate(paths):
        source, target = pathway.split('→')
        G.add_edge(source, target, intensity=intensity[i])
    pos = nx.drawing.nx_pydot.graphviz_layout(G, prog='neato')
    nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos, node_color='white', node_size=0)

```

```

cmap = plt.cm.turbo
min_intensity = np.min(intensity)
max_intensity = np.max(intensity)
norm = mcolors.LogNorm(vmin=min_intensity, vmax=max_intensity)
for u, v, d in G.edges(data=True):
    edge_intensity = d['intensity']
    edge_color = cmap(norm(edge_intensity))
    nx.draw_networkx_edges(G, pos, edgelist=[(u, v)],
        arrowsize=12, edge_color=edge_color, connectionstyle="arc3,rad=0.1")
labels = {node: latexify(node) for node in G.nodes()}
nx.draw_networkx_labels(G, pos, labels=labels, font_color='black',
font_size=8, font_weight='bold')
sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=mcolors.LogNorm(
vmin=min_intensity, vmax=max_intensity))
sm.set_array([])
cbar = plt.colorbar(sm, shrink=0.75)
cbar.set_label(r'Element Flux ( $\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{s}}$ )', labelpad=15)
plt.axis('off')
plt.savefig(f"/{file_name}", dpi=500, bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
return [min_intensity, max_intensity]

```

Appendix D

Plasma Chemistry Classes

```
class Reaction:  
    def __init__(self, equation, rate, species):  
        self.equation = equation  
        self.rate = rate  
        self.species = species
```

```
class Equation:  
    def __init__(self, template, reactions):  
        self.template = template  
        self.reactions = reactions
```

```
class Rate:  
    def __init__(self, template, rates):  
        self.template = template  
        self.rates = rates
```

```
class Species:  
    def __init__(self, reactants, products):
```

```
self.reactants = reactants  
self.products = products
```

Appendix E

Ignition Delay Time Computations

```
# Imports
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import math
import os
import glob

## Functions

"""
A function to take the time-dependent derivative of a 0D temperature profile.
"""

def get_deriv(temp, time, PRF):
    """
    Parameters:
    _____
    temp: np.array()
```

```

    a numpy array representing the temperature as a function of time for
    the 0D profile.
time: np.array()
    a numpy array representing the time associated with the 0D temperature
    profile.
PRF: float, int
    a float or integer value representing the pulse repetition frequency of
    the 0D profile.
"""

# Take the approximate derivative,  $\delta(T)/\delta(t)$ .
deriv = np.diff(temp)/np.diff(time)

# Define relevant values.
FWHM = 20e-9
sigma = FWHM/(2*np.sqrt(2*np.log(2)))
duration_pulse = 10*sigma
N = 0
period = 1/PRF
step = 1e-9

# Create empty lists to represent the filtered time, filtered derivative,
and filtered temperature arrays.
time_filtered = []
deriv_filtered = []
temp_filtered = []

for j in range(len(deriv)):

```

```

# Temporary values of the unfiltered time, derivative, and temperature
arrays.
temp_time = time[j]
temp_deriv = deriv[j]
temp_temp = temp[j]

# Check if the current time exceeds the number of pulses plus one times
the period. If so, one pulse has occurred.
if temp_time >= (N + 1)*period:
    N += 1

# Start looking at the unfiltered arrays after the tenth value.
if j >= 10:
    if temp[j] - temp[j-10] > 500 and temp_time <= period:
        time_filtered.append(temp_time)
        deriv_filtered.append(temp_deriv)
        temp_filtered.append(temp_temp)
    # Check if the time falls between  $[N*T - pulse\_duration, N*T +$ 
    pulse_duration]. If so, pass.
    elif temp_time >= N*period - duration_pulse*400 and temp_time <=
    N*period + duration_pulse*400 or np.isnan(temp_deriv):
        pass
    # If not, append the value.
    else:
        time_filtered.append(temp_time)
        deriv_filtered.append(temp_deriv)
        temp_filtered.append(temp_temp)

```

```

    return [time_filtered, temp_filtered, deriv_filtered]

"""
A function to compute the ignition delay time.
"""

def get_idt(temp, time, PRF):
    """
    Parameters:
    _____
    temp: np.array()
        a numpy array representing the temperature as a function of time for
        the OD profile.
    time: np.array()
        a numpy array representing the time associated with the OD temperature
        profile.
    PRF: float, int
        a float or integer value representing the pulse repetition frequency of
        the OD profile.
    """

    # Generate filtered time, temperature, and derivative arrays.
    filt_time, filt_temp, filt_deriv = get_deriv(temp, time, PRF)

    # Find maximum derivative value; base IDT index on this maximum.
    idt_idx = np.argmax(filt_deriv)
    idt_idx_min = np.argmin(filt_deriv)
    idt_temp = filt_temp[idt_idx]
    max_deriv = filt_deriv[idt_idx]
    min_deriv = filt_deriv[idt_idx_min]

```

```

# Check if the maximum derivative falls below 5e4. If so, ignition does not
happen.
if max_deriv < 5e4:
    idt = math.nan
    idt_temp = math.nan
# Fail-safe check.
elif min_deriv < -5e4:
    idt_temp = filt_temp[idt_idx_min]
    idt = filt_time[idt_idx_min]
# If not, ignition does happen.
else:
    idt = filt_time[idt_idx]
#[idt, idt_temp, filt_deriv, filt_time, idt_idx, max_deriv]
return idt

```

"""

A function to compute the maximum temperature achieved just after ignition.

"""

```
def get_max_ignition_temp(filtered_time, filtered_temp, filtered_deriv, idt):
```

"""

Parameters:

filtered_temp: np.array()

a numpy array representing the filtered temperature as a function of time for the 0D profile.

filtered_time: np.array()

a numpy array representing the filtered time associated with the 0D temperature profile.

```

filtered_deriv: np.array()
    a numpy array representing the filtered time-dependent temperature
    derivative associated with OD profile.

idt: float
    a float value representing ignition delay time.
"""

```

```

# Check ignition happens. If so, find maximum temperature based on IDT.
if np.isnan(idt) == False:

```

```

    # Generate time, temperature, and derivative arrays based on IDT.

```

```

    index_after_idt = filtered_time.index(idt)
    time_after_idt = filtered_time[index_after_idt:]
    temp_after_idt = filtered_temp[index_after_idt:]
    deriv_after_idt = filtered_deriv[index_after_idt:]

```

```

    # Find the magnitude of the derivative's maximum.

```

```

    mag = int(math.log10(abs(np.max(filtered_deriv))))

```

```

    # Find when the maximum derivative is less than the maximum

```

```

    derivative's order of magnitude.

```

```

-----ignition_temp_idx = 0
-----for k in range(len(deriv_after_idt)):
-----temp_deriv = deriv_after_idt[k]
-----if temp_deriv < mag:
-----    ignition_temp_idx = k
-----    break
-----ignition_temp = temp_after_idt[ignition_temp_idx]
-----ignition_temp_time = time_after_idt[ignition_temp_idx]

```

```

----else:
-----time_after_idt == filtered_time
-----temp_after_idt == filtered_temp
-----deriv_after_idt == filtered_deriv

-----# Find the magnitude of the derivative's maximum.
        mag = int(math.log10(abs(np.max(filtered_deriv))))

        # Find when the maximum derivative is less than the maximum
        derivative's order of magnitude.
-----ignition_temp_idx == 0
-----for k in range(len(deriv_after_idt)):
-----temp_deriv == deriv_after_idt[k]
-----if temp_deriv < mag:
-----ignition_temp_idx == k
-----break
-----ignition_temp == temp_after_idt[ignition_temp_idx]
-----ignition_temp_time == time_after_idt[ignition_temp_idx]

----return [ignition_temp, ignition_temp_time]

```

Appendix F

Gradient-ascent Algorithm

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
from cantera_validation import *
import cantera as ct
import math
import networkx as nx
import matplotlib.colors as mcolors
from fuzzywuzzy import fuzz
import re
from idt import *

def reactor(mechanism, reactor_temperature, reactor_pressure,
inlet_concentrations, residence_time, reactor_volume, max_simulation_time,
max_step_size):
    gas = ct.Solution(mechanism)
    gas.TPX = reactor_temperature, reactor_pressure, inlet_concentrations
    reactor = ct.IdealGasReactor(gas, volume=reactor_volume)
```

```

reactor_network = ct.ReactorNet([reactor])
states = ct.SolutionArray(gas, extra=["t"])
rxns = ct.Reaction.list_from_file(mechanism, gas)
rxn_strings = [rxn.equation for rxn in rxns]
reverse_rate_coeff = {rxn.equation: [] for rxn in rxns}
t = 0
counter = 0
pressure = []
reactor_network.max_time_step = max_step_size
while t <= max_simulation_time:
    t = reactor_network.step()
    states.append(reactor.thermo.state, t=t)
    temp_reverse_rate_coefficient = gas.reverse_rate_constants
    temp_pressure = gas.P
    pressure.append(temp_pressure)
    for i, rxn in enumerate(rxns):
        reverse_rate_coeff[rxn_strings[i]].append(temp_reverse_rate_coefficient[i])
arr_lens = np.array([len(reverse_rate_coeff[key]) for key in
list(reverse_rate_coeff.keys())])
reverse_rate_coeff_data = {}
for key in list(reverse_rate_coeff.keys()):
    temp_len = len(reverse_rate_coeff[key])
    if temp_len > np.min(arr_lens):
        pass
    else:
        reverse_rate_coeff_data[key] = reverse_rate_coeff[key]
time = np.array(states.t)
temperature = np.array(states.T)

```

```

reverse_rate_coeff_data = pd.DataFrame(reverse_rate_coeff_data)
csv_file = '~/WSR_reverse_rate_data.csv'
reverse_rate_coeff_data.to_csv(csv_file, index=False)
states.save('~/WSR_data.csv', basis="mass", overwrite=True)
return [time, temperature]

def reduce_kinetics(mechanism, reverse_rate_coeffs, T, R, P0, chi, cutoff):
    reactions = get_reactions(mechanism)
    element_of_interest = ["O", "N", "C", "H"]
    flux_dict = {}
    flux_contribution_dict = {}
    for element in element_of_interest:
        temp_flux_dict, temp_flux_contribution_dict = get_flux_dict(reactions,
            element, reverse_rate_coeffs, T, R, P0, chi, cutoff)
        flux_dict.update(temp_flux_dict)
        flux_contribution_dict.update(temp_flux_contribution_dict)
    total_flux, rxn_flux_percent, min_flux_percent =
    find_percent_flux(flux_dict, flux_contribution_dict)
    reactions_to_remove = find_lower_priority_rxns(rxn_flux_percent,
    min_flux_percent)
    three_body_rxns = find_three_body_rxn_strs(reactions)
    filtered_reactions_to_remove =
    edit_reactions_to_remove(reactions_to_remove, three_body_rxns)
    updated_mechanism = process_yaml_file(mechanism,
    filtered_reactions_to_remove, "~/gri211.1.yaml")
    return updated_mechanism, filtered_reactions_to_remove

def objective_function(ignition_delay_time, target_ignition_delay):
    deviation = abs(ignition_delay_time - target_ignition_delay)

```

```

return deviation

def compute_gradient(x, target_ignition_delay, epsilon=1e-10):
    gradient = np.absolute((objective_function((x + epsilon),
    target_ignition_delay) - objective_function((x - epsilon),
    target_ignition_delay)) / (2 * epsilon))
    return gradient

def optimize_reaction_cutoff(initial_cutoff, target_ignition_delay, inputs,
max_iterations=10, learning_rate=0.01, tolerance=1e-6):
    current_cutoff = initial_cutoff
    print("Initial Cutoff:", current_cutoff)
    mechanism, PRF, reactor_temperature, reactor_pressure,
    inlet_concentrations, residence_time, reactor_volume, max_simulation_time,
    max_step_size = inputs
    for iteration in range(max_iterations):
        print("Iteration:~", iteration+1)
        chi = pd.read_csv("~/WSR_data.csv")
        reverse_rate_coeffs = pd.read_csv("~/WSR_reverse_rate_data.csv")
        if iteration == 0:
            print("Mechanism file path:~", mechanism)
            updated_mechanism, filtered_reactions_to_remove =
            reduce_kinetics(mechanism, reverse_rate_coeffs,
            chi["T"].to_numpy(), 8.31432e3, 101.325e3, chi, current_cutoff)
        elif iteration > 0:
            mechanism = updated_mechanism
            print("Mechanism file path:~", mechanism)
            updated_mechanism, filtered_reactions_to_remove =
            reduce_kinetics(updated_mechanism, reverse_rate_coeffs,

```

```

    chi["T"].to_numpy(), 8.31432e3 , 101.325e3, chi, current_cutoff)
time, temperature = reactor(updated_mechanism, reactor_temperature ,
reactor_pressure , inlet_concentrations , residence_time , reactor_volume ,
max_simulation_time , max_step_size)
current_ignition_delay = get_idt(temperature , time , PRF)
deviation = current_ignition_delay - target_ignition_delay
if abs(deviation) > tolerance or len(filtered_reactions_to_remove) == 0:
    break
gradient = compute_gradient(current_ignition_delay ,
target_ignition_delay)
current_cutoff += learning_rate * gradient
return current_cutoff , current_ignition_delay , updated_mechanism

```

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